

Towards more Earthquake-resilient Urban Societies through a Multi-sensor-based Information System enabling Earthquake Forecasting, Early Warning and Rapid Response actions

TURNkey

Deliverable D4.4

Report on testing of automated tools and algorithms for the real-time damage detection of physical components

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Responsible Partner:	EUC
Version:	1.0
Date:	02/08/2021
Distribution level:	Public

DOCUMENT REVISION HISTORY

Date	Version	Editor	Comments
02/08/2021	1.0	Final Draft	

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GLOSSARY

Acronym	Description
SHM	Structural Health Monitoring
FDD	Frequency Domain Decomposition
EFDD	Enhanced Frequency Domain Decomposition
STFT	Short Time Fourier Transform
CWT	Continuous Wavelet Transform
ST	Stockwell Transform
SDOF	Single Degree of Freedom

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1 SCOPE AND INTRODUCTION

The objective of this document is to present the outcomes of Task 4.3, titled “*Development and testing of real-time damage detection tools for physical components*”, developed within Work Package WP4 of TURNkey project. The main aim of Task 4.3 is the development of real-time algorithms for automated damage detection, through the use of signal analysis techniques to compute variations in the dynamic properties of buildings due to damage. It is worth mentioning that in this report “real-time” refers to a timeframe in the immediate aftermath of an earthquake. Indeed, by the terminology real-time, damage detection within minutes after the event is adopted, which remains in line with the concept of rapid response to earthquakes. Therefore, the more appropriate expression is “near real-time”, adopted hereinafter. In this Deliverable, we develop and test the algorithms that will be ready for an implementation in a near-real time context.

1.1 Grant agreement aims

Task 4.3, led by EUC, started at Month 4 of the project and ended at Month 26. The outcome of Task 4.3 is Deliverable 4.4, titled “*Report on testing of automated tools and algorithms for the real time damage detection of physical components*” (i.e., the present document).

According to the Grant Agreement, Task 4.3 aimed to test existing structural health monitoring methods based on information acquired from the sensors, including the TURNkey multi-sensor unit, for near real-time damage assessment. In particular, the main objective of the planned research activities was to develop algorithms for automated damage detection, through the use of signal analysis techniques to compute variations in the system dynamic properties due to damage.

Task 4.3 is related to other relevant tasks in WP4. First of all, a link was foreseen between the measured damage indicators and the response-based performance states from Task 4.1. Moreover, the near real-time damage detection procedure delivered in Task 4.3 provides valuable in-situ information for the damage and loss updating framework in Task 4.5 and also a technical base for the onsite earthquake-early warning (EEW) of specific structures. This task aims also to facilitate the derivation of structure type-specific fragility functions for non-instrumented structures, in synergy with Task 4.1.

Since the health-monitoring sensors started to be deployed in the TURNkey test beds (TB) at the beginning of the project, Task 4.3 aims also to tests the developed algorithms with reference to recorded signals induced by earthquakes occurred within the project duration.

1.2 Structure of the deliverable

In order to achieve the aims illustrated in Section 1.1, two main activities have been carried out in the framework of Task 4.3 by the main contributing partners, i.e., EUC, UStr, BRGM, UA, and INFP:

- Activity 1: Contributing partners tested their own Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) algorithms through the comparison with recordings from a series of well-documented (benchmark) shake table tests carried out at EUC laboratories in previous initiatives. Within this framework, two noise-based (i.e., frequency and enhanced frequency domain decomposition) and two strong-motion based (i.e. Wavelet transform and Stockwell transformations) approaches were implemented and then applied. In addition, numerical simulations of the tests were carried out using both an advanced and a simplified numerical model of the test structure. The advanced model is a three-dimensional nonlinear model that describes the dynamic behaviour of the tested structure with high accuracy. The latter model consists of a simplified single degree of freedom system with elasto-plastic behaviour, whose load-displacement capacity is derived from the experimental

- tests. Those models not only served as a basis for better understanding the system response, but also provided additional data for the development of a SHM-based damage detection methodology, based on the use of the proposed signal processing techniques. Further details about the methodology are given in Section 4.
- Activity 2: Processing of signals recorded in TB (i.e., real-life applications). A database of recordings was built by collecting signals recorded during recent earthquakes especially at TB1 (Bucharest). The first set of data consists of a collection of real signals recorded on a mid-height reinforced concrete structure by broadband sensors. The second set consists of signals recorded on different types of structures (masonry and reinforced concrete buildings) monitored with RS4D sensors (belonging to the TURNkey unit). Based on the quality of data, the processing for both the datasets was carried out by adopting the approaches mentioned in Activity 1. Damage estimations were not carried out due to the weak nature of the motions. Further details about this are given in Section 5.

The structure of the Deliverable 4.4 has been defined in order to briefly and clearly illustrate the previously mentioned activities carried out in Task 4.3. Thus, after a brief state of the art in Section 2 focusing on dynamic identification techniques and definition of damage state based on dynamic identification, Section 3 illustrates the main features of the adopted approaches for dynamic identification through SHM and damage prediction. Section 4 and Section 5 focus on the activities carried out with reference to shake-table benchmark tests and to real-life applications, respectively. The main conclusions of the work are reported in Section 6, which highlights the main outcomes of the activities carried out in Task 4.3 by linking them to other tasks and WPs of TURNkey project (in particular the TURNkey platform).

2 A BRIEF STATE OF THE ART ON AVAILABLE APPROACHES

A brief state of the art is presented hereinafter by focusing on dynamic identification techniques and definition of damage state based on dynamic identification. It is important to underline that parametric system identification methods (exhaustively found in time-domain techniques) are order-dependent, besides in presence of excessive noise, they require comprehensive post-processing steps (stabilization diagrams, pole selection, clustering for automation) for confident modal parameter estimates. These techniques are based on advanced extended state-of-the-art literature involving state-space representation, however, are not tested in this research due to the time and instrumentation restraints envisioned in the project. Alternatively, techniques with low complexity and low computational costs are favoured, which would address near-real-time (e.g., pre-event vs post-event comparisons with (E)FDD) and real-time (e.g., time-frequency techniques) changes in vibration characteristics.

2.1 Dynamic identification techniques

Dynamic identification constitutes the core of vibration-based SHM methods and reflects the changes in vibration characteristics indicating structural damage sensed by instrumentation and data acquisition systems (Doebling et al., 1996). A typical dynamic identification procedure is traditionally associated with the modal parameters defining structural vibration features, including modal frequencies, damping ratios, and mode shapes. Identification of structural dynamic properties can be pursued in three main paths, which are the time-domain, frequency-domain, and time-frequency domain techniques.

Time-domain techniques heavily rely on state-space representations and have a broad range of alternative techniques. Some examples for time-domain methods could be given as random decrement (RD) method (Cole, 1973), Ibrahim time domain (ITD) (Ibrahim, 1977) and the eigen-system realization algorithm (ERA) (Juang and Pappa, 1985). These methods are widely used for damping estimation purposes. The main problem associated with many time domain methods is how to distinguish structural modes from uncorrelated modes, which are introduced to accommodate measurement noise, leakage, out-of-band modes and non-linearity, etc. This problem can cause severe errors in damping estimation.

Frequency-domain techniques are based on identifying spectral features and their counter-products associated with modal parameters. A comprehensive review on the dynamic identification and vibration-based SHM is provided by a series of comprehensive literature surveys, which describe the state-of-the-art very well (Farrar et al., 2001; Lynch and Loh, 2006; Fan and Qiao, 2011; Goyal and Pabla, 2016; Hou and Xia, 2021). As representative examples to the frequency domain methods could be given as famous frequency domain decomposition (FDD) (Brincker et al., 2001a; Brincker et 2001b) for extracting natural frequencies with associated mode shapes and its extension of enhanced frequency domain decomposition (EFDD) (Brincker et al., 2001a; Brincker et 2001b; Hasan et al., 2018) for also predicting the damping ratios by also noting that estimates of which may also be highly inaccurate/uncertain.

Time-frequency methods take the seismic response into consideration both in time and frequency domains in which a signal processing tool is used, which may be Short Time Fourier Transform (STFT), Continuous Wavelet Transform (CWT), or rather recently also Stockwell Transform (ST). Selection of approach puts an impact also on the time and frequency resolutions while processing data featuring non-stationary characteristics, such as seismic signals. Considering those approaches, we would like to note some good practices by using the CWT for modal identification of civil engineering structures in which the CWT method can decompose a signal into time-frequency domain using a mother wavelet, multi degree of freedom (MDOF) systems can be handled directly. CWT operates as a band-pass filter, and it is able to handle very noisy measurements Staszewski (1997). This method has been used successfully to extract the natural frequencies and the associated mode shapes using ambient vibration measurements of a structure (Meo et al., 2006; Le and Tamura, 2009). Regarding the damping estimation, past studies by Staszewski (1997), Hans et al. (2000), Lamarque et al. (2000) and Ta and Lardiès (2006) have highlighted that damping ratios can be estimated adequately accurate through wavelet-based logarithmic decrement for lightly damped system. However, their

studies are limited to either the impulse response or free decay response of the structures. Stockwell Transformation (ST) has been first proposed by Stockwell et al. (1996) and it may be considered as phase-corrected CWT. It preserves all the positive features of CWT with correctly localized phases and frequency-independent amplitude response (Stockwell, 2007). Good examples of practices for dynamic identification could be given as Ditomasso et al. (2012; 2015) and Pianese et al. (2018).

Prioritizing the near-real-time performance of dynamic identification techniques, this report tests novel time-frequency techniques for inferring the change of dynamic characteristics in an online setting and also benchmarks these near-real-time estimations with the commonly used frequency-domain technique, named, Frequency Domain Decomposition (FDD) and its extension into damping estimation called enhanced-FDD (EFDD). These identification techniques are initially applied to a large-scale shaking table test and then to existing buildings in Bucharest, Romania to explore their advantages and disadvantages, described further in the next section.

2.2 Identification of damage state following dynamic identification

Damage identification literature is broad in the way it expresses the existence, location, extent, and associated consequences of damage (Rytter, 1993). From vibration based SHM perspective, the primary SHM step (*existence*) answers the question “is there any damage?” and is followed by the *location* query “where is the damage?” and the *extent* investigating “what is the extent of the damage?”. And the ultimate question (*consequences*) looks for an answer to the question “what is the remaining useful life of the structure?”. And the ultimate question looks for an answer to the question “what is the remaining useful life of the structure?”. In case of seismic damage, there is a similarity between the SHM-based damage assessment process and the data-based damage classification. The difference is that in the former the sensors signals are post-processed to identify the change of frequency and a model is then used to relate this change to damage, whereas in the latter machine learning approaches are used directly on sensor data to infer damage. From the practical point of view, the damage identified from the sensor, and expressed by the change of frequency, whatever method is used, should be related to the observational damages used by the Civil Protection for identifying the damage state during crisis management. Referring to the European Macroseismic Scale (EMS98, Grünthal et al., 1998), five grades of damage can be observed on structural and non-structural components of civil infrastructure subject to seismic damage. These damage grades cover a broad range starting from fine cracks on the building components (Damage Grade 1) to large-cracks, rebar fracture, near-collapse, and collapse of the structure (Damage Grade 4-5). In the latter sections (Sections 3.2.1, 3.2.3, 4.3.2 and 4.6), EMS98 is followed to state the damage descriptions and vibration-based replicas are presented to provide a connection between dynamic identification results and seismic damage states through a large-scale seismic shaking table study presented in Section 4.

Finally, we would like to highlight the work of Goulet et al. (2015) in which the Authors first compiled the available information in the literature (see Figure 2.1) in terms of frequency reduction after a seismic event and EMS98 damage grade. Their database includes principally reinforced concrete structures of low-rise (2 storeys) to mid-high rise (10 storeys), but also include data points for other typologies (such as one data point with steel frame with masonry infills). Then, they developed a Bayesian updating framework to learn and make the calculations considering the building characteristics of a particular city under consideration. Connecting the SHM-based frequency reduction to EMS-98 damage grades for a building typology representative in TURNkey testbeds, this study becomes very useful to be referred in the current work.

Figure 2.1: Database of EMS98 damage grade – f/f_0 relation assembled (after Goulet et al., 2015)

3 UTILIZED APPROACHES FOR DYNAMIC IDENTIFICATION AND DAMAGE PREDICTION

This Section illustrates the main features of the approaches adopted for dynamic identification through SHM and afterwards damage prediction using the results obtained in SHM. For SHM, two noise-based (i.e., frequency and enhanced frequency domain decomposition) and two strong-motion based (i.e., Wavelet and Stockwell transformations) approaches were implemented and then applied. For damage prediction, three different approaches are followed based on the knowledge level.

3.1 Dynamic identification

3.1.1 Vibration-based approaches

One of the benchmark vibration-based techniques referred to this report is the Frequency Domain Decomposition (FDD) and its successor Enhanced Frequency Domain Decomposition (EFDD). Developed by Brincker et al. (2001a), FDD is an intuitive frequency-domain method suitable for modal identification under operational conditions. FDD is an output-only technique assuming the system input is white noise and relies on synchronous acquisition of multi-channel dynamic response data from the structure of interest for identification of modal frequencies and mode shapes. The method utilizes Power Spectral Density (PSD) matrix of the multi-channel response as a function of frequency and performs singular value decomposition to get the maximum eigenvalues observed on the frequency domain. Where the eigenvalues are maximized, eigenvectors provide the mode shapes corresponding to discrete frequencies. Equation 3.1 expresses the core FDD equation decomposing the PSD matrix into its eigenvalues and eigenvectors, efficient in identifying modal frequencies and mode shapes, respectively.

$$S_{yy}(w) = U(w) \cdot \Sigma(w) \cdot U^H(w) \quad (3.1)$$

Where $S_{yy}(w)$ is the power spectral density matrix of the response vector y , $U(w)$ is the unitary matrix of the singular vectors, $\Sigma(w)$ is the diagonal matrix of the singular values, and H denotes complex conjugate and transpose. In EFDD, after carrying out Singular Value Decomposition, inversion from frequency spectra back into time series to obtain autocorrelation functions representative of the structural dynamics of single degree of freedom systems to which the original structure may be decomposed. By means of proper interpolation procedures operating on the autocorrelation functions, damping ratios and natural frequencies could be jointly inverted. Vibrating modes are also identified starting from the singular vectors belonging to the neighbourhood of each peak that was previously identified (Brincker et 2001b; Hasan et al., 2018).

3.1.2 Ground motion-based approaches

3.1.2.1 Continuous wavelet transform based approach

This section provides a brief description of the theoretical background of the wavelet transform-based dynamic identification technique. The interested readers should refer directly to the key references to understand the theoretical background of the method (e.g., Rioul and Vetterli, 1991; Chui, 1992; Daubechies, 1992). Fourier transformation linearly transforms a given function $x(t)$ from the time domain into the frequency domain using a basic function $e^{-j\omega t}$, according to the following equation:

$$FT_{[x]} = \int_{-\alpha}^{\alpha} x(t) e^{-j\omega t} dt \quad (3.2)$$

This transformation does not include any local time information of the function $x(t)$. Initially, Fourier transformation of the short time sliding window is used to overcome this limitation by decomposing the

function into frequency-time domain. However, this method called Short Time Fourier Transformation (STFT) suffers from time-frequency resolution limitation. Later, Continuous Wavelet Transform (CWT) method is developed to obtain better spectral decomposition, as an alternative method to STFT. The basic idea of the CWT method is to find a function $\psi(t)$, which can generate a basis for the entire domain of function $x(t)$, if a function $x(t)$ satisfies the condition that $x(t)$ decays to zero at $\pm\alpha$ as in the case of Fourier transform. The fast decay in time domain and the limited band width in frequency domain introduces locality into the analysis, which is not the case of Fourier transform where a global representation can only be obtained. The function $\psi(t)$, called wavelet, must satisfy the two admissibility conditions: (1) it must be absolutely integrable and square integrable and (2) it must be band limited and have zero mean. Then, using wavelets, the CWT method can be used to decompose a function $x(t)$ into frequency-time domain as defined in the following form:

$$W_{(a,b)} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{a}} \int_{-\alpha}^{+\alpha} x(t) \psi^* \left(\frac{t-b}{a} \right) dt \quad (3.3)$$

where $\psi^*(t)$ and b are the complex conjugate of $\psi(t)$ and the parameter localizing the wavelet function in the time domain, respectively and $W_{(a,b)}$ are the CWT coefficients that represent the measure of the similitude between the function $x(t)$ and the wavelet at the time b and the scale a .

The complex Morlet wavelet which is commonly used for continuous wave transform as a basic function can be expressed as in Eq. 3.4 and its Fourier transform can be expressed as in Eq. 3.5. The band with parameter F_b is selected to optimize the time and frequency resolution.

$$\psi(t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi F_b}} e^{2\pi i f_c t} e^{-\frac{t^2}{F_b}} \quad (3.4)$$

$$\tilde{\psi}(af) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi F_b}} e^{(F_b \pi^2 (af - f_c)^2)} \quad (3.5)$$

where f and f_c are Fourier frequency and central wavelet frequency.

The conversion between Fourier frequency and the scale a can be established as (Eq.3.6):

$$f = \frac{f_s f_c}{a} \quad (3.6)$$

where f_s and a are the sampling frequency and the scale, respectively.

This is not performed in this study, but for future works, using the CWT method, which decomposes the signal $x(t)$ into time-frequency domain, wavelet energy for each scale a can be estimated (Negulescu et al., 2013). Wavelet energy is a complementary parameter to the frequency, that can be retrieved from the CWT method and that could take into account the effects of number of inelastic cycles to the damage.

Wijesundara et al. (2012) and Negulescu et al. (2013) applied CWT for the estimation of modal properties of existing structures using ambient excitation measurements. The dynamic equilibrium equation of a SDOF system can be expressed as:

$$m\ddot{x} + c\dot{x} + kx = f(t) \quad (3.7)$$

where m , c and k are mass, damping and the stiffness of the SDOF system. Considering the SDOF system as described by Eq. 3.6, the damped free vibration of a under damped system can be represented in the following form:

$$x(t) = A(t)e^{\pm i\omega_n \sqrt{1-\zeta^2}t} = A(t)e^{i\phi(t)} \quad (3.8)$$

where $A(t)$ is the decaying envelope of the free vibration response of the SDOF system. It can also be expressed in the following form as:

$$A(t) = A_0 e^{-\zeta\omega_n t} \quad (3.9)$$

where ζ is damping ratio and A_0 is the initial amplitude of the response.

For the Morlet wavelet function, the modulus of CWT coefficients can be approximated as (Staszewski, 1997):

$$|W_{(a,b)}| \approx A(b) \left| G^*(a\dot{\phi}(b)) \right| \quad (3.10)$$

Combining Eqs. 3.8, 3.9 and 3.10 and given value of a_0 , the following relationship can be determined:

$$|W_{(a_0,b)}| \approx A_0 e^{-\zeta\omega_n b} \left| G^*(\pm a_0 i \omega_n \sqrt{1-\zeta^2}) \right| \quad (3.11)$$

Taking the logarithm of both sides in Eq. 3.11, one obtains:

$$\ln |W_{(a_0,b)}| \approx -\zeta\omega_n b + \ln \left(A_0 \left| G^*(\pm a_0 i \omega_n \sqrt{1-\zeta^2}) \right| \right) \quad (3.12)$$

Therefore, the damping ratio ζ of the system can be estimated from the slope of the straight line of the wavelet modulus cross using Eq 3.13:

$$\zeta = \frac{1}{2\pi m} \ln \left| \frac{W_{(a_0,b)}}{W_{(a_0,b+mT_0)}} \right| \quad (3.13)$$

The wavelet ridges are formed at an instantaneous frequency and time when the frequency of the response at a time is equal to the frequency of the dilated mother wavelet. Therefore, natural frequencies are evaluated by extracting a window parallel to the frequency axis of time-frequency plot at wavelet ridges where the CWT coefficients reach their maximum values.

3.1.2.2 Stockwell transform based approach

Stockwell transform (S-Transform) could be considered as the phase-corrected counterpart of the wavelet transform (Stockwell et al., 1996). In other words, the wavelet transform, $W(\tau, f)$, is multiplied by the phase factor.

$$S(\tau, f) = e^{i2\pi f\tau} W(\tau, f) \quad (3.14)$$

$$W(\tau, f) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} h(t) \omega(t - \tau, d) dt \quad (3.15)$$

In this equation, t is the time and f the frequency, τ is the length of the time interval, W is the wavelet transform of any function $h(t)$ by using the replica of the mother wavelet, $\omega(t, d)$ with d representing the dilation which is directly related to the resolution.

In the formulation, Stockwell et al. (1996) uses Gaussian window as the parent wavelet function due to the effectiveness and correctness of Gaussian function because of: (1) its capacity to minimize the quadratic time-frequency moment around time-frequency point; (2) property of symmetricity in time and frequency (hence ease at calculating the Fourier transforms); (3) not having any artefact in its local maxima. Details may be addressed from Stockwell (2007). Adopting the Gaussian parent wavelet function, the open form of S-transform could be derived as below.

$$S(\tau, f) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} h(t) \frac{|f|}{\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{(\tau-t)^2 f^2}{2}} e^{-i2\pi f t} dt \quad (3.16)$$

Stockwell (2007) explains that the *voice*, $S(\tau, f_0)$, represents the temporal change of any constant frequency content, whereas the *local spectrum*, is the distribution of the frequency content at any snapshot in time domain.

Discrete S-Transform becomes useful when dealing with nonstationary and random signals, such as the acceleration recordings at instrumented locations. It is defined as below:

$$S \left[jT, \frac{n}{NT} \right] = \sum_{m=-N/2}^{N/2-1} H \left[\frac{m+n}{NT} \right] e^{-\frac{2\pi^2 m^2}{n^2}} e^{\frac{i2\pi m j}{N}}; j, m, n \in 1, 2, \dots, N-1 \quad (3.17)$$

$$S[jT, 0] = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} h[kT]; n = 0 \quad (3.18)$$

In those equations, H is the Fourier transform of N -point time series $h[kT]$, $S[jT, j/NT]$ is the discrete Stockwell transform component at time index jT and frequency index n/NT for any j and n .

Implementation of the Stockwell Transform into numerical domain is explained by Stockwell (2007) as follows:

- Calculation the Fourier transform of N point time series,
- Spectrum is shifted such that the voice frequency becomes the new “zero”,
- Shifted frequency is multiplied with Gaussian voice,
- N point inverse Fourier transform is carried out to return to time domain
- Above points are repeated until all necessary voices are computed.

An example computation of an example chirp signal is provided in below (Figure 3.1):

Figure 3.1: Example application of Stockwell transform by using an input chirp signal

Applications of S-Transform are noteworthy in signal processing among various areas (such as Jones et al., 2006; Dehghani, 2009), the use of it in earthquake engineering is somewhat still limited, few examples include the dynamic identification by Ditomasso et al. (2012), determination of the time of liquefaction by Kramer et al. (2016), SHM purposes by Amezcuita-Sanchez and Adeli (2016), identification of nonlinear structural response by Pianese et al. (2018).

In this work, by exploiting its frequency-independent correct amplitude identification and accurate phase localization features, we are using S-Transform in an innovative mean, through computing the time-dependent amplification function to detect the natural fundamental vibration period of monitored structures exposed to linear and nonlinear deformation regimes. This is achieved through calculating the absolute values of the S-transforms of the signals recorded at roof and foundation levels, then taking the ratio of computed S-transform matrices at each pair of time and frequency, hence determining the amplification function (AF) as in Eq. 3.19.

$$AF[jt, kf] = \frac{|S_{top}[jt, kf]|}{|S_{bot}[jt, kf]|} \quad (3.19)$$

After taking this ratio, maxima of amplifications of the local spectra are found which becomes the natural frequency of the system at that instant. Possible problems associated with singularities due to near-zero amplitudes are fixed through applying a maximum cap for the amplification function (a number between 1 to 50 based on the amplitudes present in the (AF) and standard outlier filtering techniques when the identified frequency does not agree with the ones in the vicinity. It is important to note that, likewise in other SHM approaches, it is important to know the order of magnitude of the expected vibration frequency, hence upper and lower bounds are provided to define an interval in which the vibration frequency is to be searched. Once the trend of change in time-dependent vibration frequencies is decided, the value of frequency reduction (or period elongation) is used to estimate the damage level or to provide input for the numerical model under consideration. It is noteworthy to mention that damping ratio assessment is carried out in terms of the best fitting single degree of freedom amplification function to the spectral ratio of Fourier amplitudes considering the top and foundation signals. In this respect, the nature of damping ratio is an average value, and it is not time dependent.

3.2 Damage detection following dynamic identification

Three different approaches are proposed for damage estimation using sensor data, based on the available knowledge levels of the structure, namely a basic, intermediate, and a comprehensive approach. Among these approaches, in particular the empirical one is tailored to reinforced concrete (RC) building stock which is compatible with the structures monitored in testbeds.

1. Basic (empirical) approach. In this method, database of empirical observations presented in Goulet et al. (2015) is associated with the sensor-based identification of the fundamental vibration frequency, before and after a seismic event, obtained through sensor data. Goulet et al. (2015), collected the outcomes of a series of studies reporting the frequencies of vibration of buildings before and after an earthquake, and the frequency change related to the level of damage sustained by the building, expressed in terms of the European Macroseismic Scale (EMS) 98. This scale has 5 damage indices (1 to 5) plus index 0 for no damage. The dataset collects information essentially from RC buildings with different heights and characteristics, with some exceptions (such as steel-brick structures; Omori, 1922). This approach does not require knowledge of the building characteristics, but it returns damage estimates with elevated uncertainty. Further details of the method are presented in Section 3.2.1. To follow this approach, minimum level of data availability (LoDA) defined in Deliverable D4.1, should be 1 or 2.
2. Numerical approach. This method combines the results of numerical analyses of the structural systems with the results of the application of dynamic identification techniques to sensor data. There are two different subclasses:
 - Use of idealized SDOF numerical model. In this approach, the structure is represented by a single degree of freedom equivalent system. Once the load-displacement response is defined, the hysteretic response is carried out according to HHS method presented in Borzi et al. (2001). This branch is compatible with the intermediate level of knowledge in which the pushover curve could be constructed. Flowchart is presented in Section 3.2.2 and further details are presented in Section 4.5.1. To follow this approach, minimum level of data availability (LoDA) defined in Deliverable D4.1, should be 3.
 - Use of detailed numerical model. Complete model is constructed with accurate representation of the geometry, connectivity, member load-deformation responses. In this approach, a model updating technique is used to re-calibrate the stiffness of the entire system and/or damaged elements. This branch is compatible with comprehensive level of knowledge of the system, including material properties, geometry, and element connection details. A Flowchart illustrated the method is presented in Section 3.2.2 and further details are given in Section 4.5.2. To follow this approach, minimum level of data availability (LoDA) defined in Deliverable D4.1, should be much higher than 3.
3. Analytical approach. In this method, the concept of secant-stiffness is used to relate the reductions in vibration frequencies with the expected ductility demand. There are two main assumptions of this method: the use of secant stiffness to represent the deformation-compatible stiffness of the system and absence of accumulated displacement in the assessment of ductility demand. Like 2a, required knowledge level is intermediate. Further details are presented in Section 3.2.3. To follow this approach, minimum level of data availability (LoDA) defined in Deliverable D4.1, should be 3.

It is noted that the use of approaches 2 and 3 requires setting limit states thresholds. Thresholds are associated through the use of Lagomarsino and Giovinazzi (2006) approach, which are defined in terms of displacement ductility of the structural system ($\mu_d=d/d_y$) values shown below in Equation (3.20). Corresponding grades DS1, DS2, DS3, and DS4 stand for slight, moderate, extensive, and complete damage, which can be then restated as EMS98 damage grades 1, 2, 3, and ≥ 4 , respectively.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mu_d &= 0.7 && \text{for EMS98 damage grade} = 1 \\
 \mu_d &= 1.5 && \text{for EMS98 damage grade} = 2 \\
 \mu_d &= 0.5(1 + \mu_u) && \text{for EMS98 damage grade} = 3 \\
 \mu_d &= \mu_u && \text{for EMS98 damage grade} \geq 4
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{3.20}$$

Where, yield (d_y) and ultimate displacement (d_u) thresholds may be structure or typology specific.

3.2.1 Empirical approach

In this approach, empirical database of frequency reduction-observed damage presented in Goulet et al. (2015) is used. First, the data points in Figure 2.1 are digitized. Then, frequency reduction intervals are created by assuming an interval width of 0.2, in other words 4 intervals are created: [0.20,0.40), [0.40-0.60), [0.60-0.80), and [0.80-1.00]. Upon binning the discrete data, damage probabilities within each interval are calculated through normalization of the occurrence numbers with total number of observations within that interval, and consequently damage probability histograms are created as shown in Figure 3.2, shown below.

Figure 3.2: Histogram of probability of damage occurrence as a function of frequency reduction

In order to provide a continuous predictor, each probability of occurrence value is idealized with its central value, i.e., $f_i/f_0=0.3$ for the interval of [0.2,0.4). By converting f_i/f_0 to T_i/T_0-1 , familiar Gaussian cumulative density curves are created to stand for damage functions, as shown in Figure 3.3, relating the probability of being in a given damage state to be exceeded to the reduction of frequency (or elongation of the period).

Figure 3.3: Continuous damage functions versus sensor-based period elongation proxy. T_i : period of vibration during/after the i^{th} ground motion in the sequence. T_0 : initial (undamaged) natural vibration period

For a given T_i/T_0 , the probability of having any damage grade i (DG_i) could be found as shown below. (Eq. 3.21). Obviously, applying this method a very uncertain damage estimate is obtained, reflecting the lack of knowledge of the building properties.

$$P[D = DG_i] = P[D \geq DG_i] - P[D \geq DG_{i+1}] \text{ for } i=0, 1, 2, 3$$

$$P[D = DG_4 \text{ or } D = DG_5] = P[D \geq DG_5] \quad (3.21)$$

Where DG_i is the damage grade with $P[D \geq D_0] = 1$.

3.2.2 Numerical approach

In this section, two flowcharts are provided with the use of numerical approaches under consideration for simplified (Figure 3.4) and detailed numerical modelling (Figure 3.5). In the former, the model is set up in terms of an equivalent single degree of freedom (SDOF) system, of which the load-displacement curve is provided. While defining the initial line of the tri-linear load-displacement curve, small strain (uncracked) stiffness is used. Yield displacement/ultimate displacements as well as the strength are set as structure or typology specific values. The feedback mechanism provides an iterative scheme, in case an inaccurate estimation is made for a seismic event initial parameters may be readjusted until a good agreement in damage states are obtained. With this manner, the model waits for the next event (which may be an aftershock or another mainshock).

Figure 3.4: Flowchart to be used for simplified numerical approach

In the case of a full (or detailed) numerical modelling approach, the model setup phase is more detailed and considers accurate definitions of mass, stiffness, and strength characteristics of members and connections. Then, after the earthquake occurs, sensor data is used to update stiffness of the entire system with a representative stiffness multiplier until the Eigenvalue solution matches the new frequency. It should be underlined that this method requires expert person interaction, and it is not compatible with near-real time use. On the other hand, it stays as a good tool to verify the accuracy of the faster methods.

Figure 3.5: Flowchart to be used for detailed numerical approach

3.2.3 Analytical approach

In the analytical approach, the capacity curve is converted into a frequency-displacement curve (Figure 3.6) based on the concept of effective secant stiffness, which is defined for at a given displacement d by the ratio $k_{\text{sec}}(d) = \frac{F(d)}{d}$ between the force $F(d)$ at that displacement level and d .

The fundamental frequency for a given displacement demand is obtained as $\omega^2(d) = \frac{k_{\text{sec}}(d)}{m^*}$, where m^* is the mass of a single-degree-of-freedom system equivalent to the building. This corresponds to the participating mass for the vibration mode considered in the pushover analysis, defined as $m^* = \sum_i m_i \phi_i$. For $d < d_y$, the circular

vibration frequency is defined by $\omega_0^2 = \frac{k_{in}(d)}{m}$, whereas when the system reaches the ultimate displacement,

$\omega_u^2 = \frac{k_{\text{sec}}(d_u)}{m^*} = \frac{\omega_0^2 d_y}{d_u}$. Thus, based on this simplified approach, for a system with ductility capacity 4 the

fundamental frequency is expected to reduce by half when the system attains the ultimate displacement level which corresponds to roughly DG3 (see Figure 3.3). Obviously, this relationship is based on a series of simplifying assumptions, the most important one being the fact that the degraded stiffness of the system at the end of the earthquake may differ significantly from the secant stiffness at the maximum displacement.

Figure 3.6: Relationship between frequency change and seismic displacement demand

4 EUCENTRE SHAKE TABLE BENCHMARK TESTS

As mentioned in the introduction, contributing partners in Task 4.3 tested their own SHM algorithms for dynamic identification through the comparison with recordings from a series of well-documented (benchmark) shake table tests carried out at EUC laboratories in past initiatives. Indeed, the approaches presented in Section 3.2, were implemented and applied. In addition, efforts were spent in nonlinear numerical modelling of the test structure. Numerical analyses were performed by considering both simplified and complete configurations. Those models not only served as a basis for better understanding the system response, but also provided additional data for testing SHM algorithms under consideration. As the final step, a general methodology for near real-time damage detection based on the use of signal processing techniques has been set up.

4.1 Definition of the model structure

The building specimen studied in these tests is a 1:2 scaled, 4-story reinforced concrete (RC) / unreinforced masonry (URM) building subject to uniaxial excitation through shaking table tests performed at the EUCENTRE Laboratories (Beyer et al. 2015). Combination of RC and URM wall lateral resisting mechanism provides a healthy combination of the building stock present in TURNkey testbeds, thus, becomes a good case study for sensor-informed damage detection methods.

In the model structure, each story consists of a 1400 mm clear height and a slab thickness of 150 mm. Sum of structural (34.9 t) and externally added masses (34.9 t) add up to 69.8 t. Superstructure concrete type, foundation concrete type, and steel reinforcement classes are given as C28/35, C40/50, and B450C, respectively. Representative samples from the concrete and masonry parts express an elasticity modulus of 24.1 GPa and 5.5 GPa.

The structure is symmetric along the north-south axis, asymmetric along east-west axis, and regular over height. The shaking table excitations are performed uniaxially in the north-south axis, where north-south walls experience out-of-plane, and east-west walls experience in-plane loading. Shake table dynamic force capacity is equal to 1720 kN and the maximum base shear demand experienced throughout the tests is 757 kN. In summary, the building has a height of 6200 mm and an approximate area of 5560x3200 mm². Figure 4.1 shows the plan and three-dimensional view drawings, and a pre-test photograph showing the structure resting on the shaking table.

Figure 4.1: Building views: a) north b) west c) south d) 3D e) top f) photograph (in mm) by Beyer et al. (2015)

The URM walls were built with half-scale clay brick blocks made especially for the project. The walls were constructed using standard mortar of class M15; the thickness of the horizontal and vertical mortar joints was 5 mm thick. The URM walls were 95 mm thick. After an experimental campaign comparing the behaviour of URM walls at full-scale and half-scale, the brick units used to build the URM walls were chosen (Petry and Beyer, 2014). The geometry and reinforcing arrangement of the two RC walls were identical (Figure 4.2). The

thickness of the RC slabs was 150 mm. The slab's top and bottom reinforcements were made of a steel net with D10 mm bars spaced at 100 mm intervals. Beyer et al. (2015) provided further details and a complete description of the physical model.

Figure 4.2: Reinforcement layout of RC walls: elevation (left) and cross-sections (right); all measures are in mm Beyer et al. (2015)

The building is instrumented with numerous kinds of sensors including 20 accelerometers, 49 displacement transducers, 24 omega gages, and 492 optical markers on the west façade (see Figure 4.3). In other words, the measurements are classified into two as conventional and optical sensing systems. Two kinds of dynamic tests are pursued: white noise and earthquake excitations. For the conventional systems, the earthquake sampling rate is set to 1024 Hz, whereas white noise excitations have a reduced rate equal to 256 Hz. For the optical systems, 60 Hz sampling rate is followed, and distributed optical data are combined through a synchronization scheme using matching markers and up sampling.

Potentiometer 49 is connected to the floor representing the table displacement and accelerometers 1, 2, and 3 corresponds to table accelerations. The rest of the accelerometers are distributed to the floors as 5&6 (first), 9&10 (second), 13&14 (third), and 17&18 (fourth) in the shaking direction measuring in-plane responses. The remainder accelerometers present out-of-plane vibrations as a response to the white noise and earthquake excitations. An optical system consisting of 10 cameras are used to record 70 markers with a 0.2 m gridline, and 48 markers are fixed to the slab and foundation. The marker labels follow a camera no / marker no layout labelled from left to right, top to bottom. The camera coordinate system is equivalent to X-axis north and Y-axis upwards.

Being open access on Zenodo (Tondelli et al., 2014; <https://zenodo.org/record/11578>), pre-processed conventional test measurements are composed of 97 columns (2-4 shake table, 5-24 accelerometer, 25-73 potentiometers, and 74-97 omega gages). White noises are imposed at 0.05 m/s² amplitude before each earthquake except Test 7. The optical dataset consists of 1219 columns following x and y coordinate order and naming based on camera/marker/coordinate (e.g., 5.10.x). With postprocessing, conventional dataset increases to 101 columns where the 98th-100th columns are base shear estimates, and the 101st column is relative top displacement. Postprocessing includes a Butterworth low-pass filter at 40 Hz.

Figure 4.3 shows the accelerometer and marker distributions throughout the building structure. Specimen level (drawings), experiment level (photos and videos), signal level (conventional and optical data specifications),

and nine tests for each unprocessed and processed time series are publicly available on Tondelli et al. (2014). The reader can refer to Beyer et al. (2015) for further details on the tests.

Figure 4.3: Accelerometer and optic marker distributions of building instrumentation after Beyer et al. (2015). All the accelerometric data are used in this report

4.2 Model setup and testing

The building structure considered in these tests is exposed to a repetitive series of input ground motions, 1979 Montenegro Earthquake from European Strong Motion Database, with amplified intensities. Motions are scaled from 0.05 g to 0.9 g forming nine sequential tests from minor damage to near collapse states. Between each earthquake event, white noise excitations (except WN7) are conducted. Figure 4.4 presents the consecutive input ground motions, and Table 4.1 summarizes the ground motion intensities. Throughout each test, acceleration and displacement response is collected through accelerometers and vision-based sensing. Figure 4.5 shows the engineering demand parameters in the time domain. Table 4.2 expresses the engineering demand parameters observed per each test. The data is made available online by Tondelli et al. (2014).

Figure 4.4: Input ground motions from the shaking table tests

Table 4.1: Summary of shaking table tests involving intensity measure and damage observed

Test No (EQ)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
PeakGroundAcceleration(g)	0.08	0.13	0.21	0.36	0.41	0.76	0.37	0.64	1.52

Figure 4.5: Earthquake response time histories

Table 4.2: Summary of engineering demand parameters observed

Test No	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
PeakFloorAcceleration(g)	0.14	0.29	0.55	0.57	0.64	1.08	0.68	1.07	1.29
ResidualDriftRatio (%)	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.29
TransientDriftRatio (%)	0.03	0.04	0.08	0.08	0.13	0.33	0.18	0.47	1.39

4.3 Outputs of interest from the relevant publication and dataset

4.3.1 Load-displacement (pushover) response

Load-displacement response of the R/C wall structure with URM walls has been primarily obtained through experimental dynamic data by Beyer et al. (2015), which is provided in Figure 4.6 below with total building height of 6.2 m and weight of 682 kN as noted in Section 4.2.

Figure 4.6: Experimental load-displacement values (from Beyer et al., 2015)

4.3.2 Elongation of T_0 and assigned damage states

In Beyer et al. (2015), values shown in the table below are reported for the damaged natural vibration periods and assigned damage grades. It is noted that in the article of reference, no distinction between D0 (no damage) and D1 (slight damage) has been done. Due to this reason, D1 values are represented by $\leq D1$. It is noted that during the experimental campaign period of vibration of the structures had been measured using white noise information (before the test) and accelerometric data during the test. Both period inversions are reported here, the former will be used for FDD, EFDD, and Wavelet transform based interpretations while the latter will be used for Wavelet and Stockwell transform based interpretations.

Table 4.3: Synthesis of results extracted from Beyer et al. (2015). Before test identification of vibration period was made by using white noise information, during test identification of vibration period was made by using accelerometric data. Damage grades (DG) are according to EMS98. All periods are in seconds

Test no	Before test vibration period (sec)	During test vibration period (sec)	DG (EMS-98)	Test no	Before test vibration period (sec)	During test vibration period (sec)	DG (EMS-98)
1	0.13	0.13	$\leq D1$	6	0.17	0.23	D2
2	0.13	0.14	$\leq D1$	7	-	0.22	D2
3	0.13	0.15	$\leq D1$	8	0.19	0.26	D3
4	0.15	0.15	D2	9	0.21	0.29	$\geq D4$
5	0.16	0.14	D2				

4.4 Elaboration of the experimental signal level data through SHM methods

4.4.1 Through FDD and EFDD based method

The white noise tests before and after each seismic test propose suitable data to quantify the modal parameter differences between pre-event and post-event states. As explained before, FDD/EFDD technique is used to identify the modal frequencies, mode shapes, and damping ratios before and after each earthquake. Figure 4.7 summarizes the modal frequencies and mode shapes obtained from each white noise test (from 1 to 8 excluding 7).

Due to their very similar nature of implementation, EFDD results show similar results with respect to FDD counterpart. Results of singular value decomposition (SVD) of all tests are provided in a unified figure below (Figure 4.8). It is noted that WN5 did not provide a frequency shift as supposed due to a hole in input frequency content around 6-6.5 Hz. Inversions of the damping ratios do not show a meaningful trend, they are directly reported in Table 4.10.

Figure 4.8 shows that the main frequency does not seem to have a classical linear degradation but rather jumps of the frequency associated to linear degradation to each jump. This can be explained by the fact that the building changes the mode of behaviour/response from the Test 1 to the Test 9 due to its cumulated damages.

Figure 4.7: Exemplary singular values and related mode shapes. Top row: WN 1 and 2, second row: WN 3 and 4, third row: WN 5 and 6, last row: WN 8 and WN 9)

Figure 4.8: SVD results obtained from EFDD algorithm

4.4.2 Through Continuous wavelet transform based method

The Wavelet approach was used for estimation of the frequencies from the White Noise (WN), from the last 10 seconds of the records (so-called tail or coda in the document) and for the estimation of the damping values. The WN or the last 10 seconds of the record (approximated to the free decay response) are decomposed into a time-frequency domain by using CWT with a complex Morlet wavelet. In order to identify the natural frequencies, windows parallel to the frequency axis at the wavelet ridges in time-frequency plot are extracted. The peak value of the modulus of CWT coefficients corresponds to the frequency of the building. Therefore, the procedure used to estimate the period and the damping through the wavelet analysis included the following main steps:

- Transforming the time signal into time-frequency domain (Figure 4.9) by using the complex wavelet transform (for all the length of the record for representation).
- Detecting the wavelet ridges in the wavelet plot to estimate the natural frequencies/periods T_i
- Extracting the wavelet envelop at a natural period T_i (Figure 4.10).
- Calculating the damping ratios according to the Eq (3.13).

Figure 4.9: Transforming the time signal into time-frequency domain using wavelet approach

With reference to the response of the building tested on the EUCENTRE shake table, the behaviour mode changes during the Test 9. The latter can be explained by using the wavelet analysis, as follows:

- From Tests T1 to T3: One main period and shift of it from 0.13 to 0.16 sec; same behaviour of the structure.
- From Tests T4 to T6: Appearing of periods 0.22 and 0.33 with vanishing of the period 0.14 sec; change of the behaviour response certainly due to the appearance of the first damages.
- Tests T7 to T9: response of the building on the periods 0.22 and 0.33sec. In this case, in the future, some adaptations of the wavelet parameters can bring more clear information on the behaviour of the structure.

Figure 4.10: Extracting the wavelet envelop at a natural period T_i for each of the 9 Tests: Left: all superposed. Right: one by one

Table 4.4: Summary of identified modal frequencies per test (from ground motion –tail data and WN) in longitudinal direction

Test No	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Tail Eq Wavelet	7.19	6.78	6.66	6.66	6.92	3.67	4.63	3.09	2.56
WN Wavelet	8.17	7.83	7.68	6.56	5.92	6.29	-	5.18	4.98

Table 4.5: Summary of identified modal frequencies per test (from ground motion –tail data) in transversal direction

Test No (WN)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Tail Eq Wavelet	9.51	9.12	8.78	8.65	8.55	7.87	8.02	7.56	-

Furthermore, a window paralleled to the time axis at the wavelet ridge is extracted from the time-frequency plot to estimate the damping ratio corresponding to the mode of vibration of the building using Eq (3.13). We used this method of damping estimation is used for the tail of the earthquake (Figure 4.11) and for the WN. The values obtained for damping are not always consistent. Unfortunately, the damping estimation is quite a tricky issue and it needs more detailed treatments. In order to overcome some inconsistencies, in some cases (italic values in the Tables 4.6) we evaluate the RD signature of the signal is evaluated using the RD method before performing the damping calculation. The RD signature, hence obtained, is then decomposed into time-frequency domain using CWT; a window parallel to the time axis is extracted at the wavelet ridge and then the semi-logarithmic plot of the CWT coefficient modulus is obtained (Figure 4.12). However, at this stage, the damping ratio evaluated using wavelet approach cannot be used for the health monitoring of buildings.

Figure 4.11: Left- tail of signal of the T6, Central- semi-logarithmic plot of the CWT coefficient modulus, Right time-frequency plot.

Figure 4.12: Left- RD signature of the complete signal of the T3, Central- semi-logarithmic plot of the CWT coefficient modulus, Right time-frequency plot.

Table 4.6: Summary of identified damping per test (from ground motion –tail data and from WN) in longitudinal direction

Test No.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
EQ. Tail Damp, North Wall (17)	0.92	-	2.64	2.88	5.65	3.80	3.42	4.86	4.85
EQ. Tail Damp, South Wall (18)	0.86	-	3.21	2.66	5.50	3.79	3.52	4.37	5.58
WN Damp, North Wall (17)	1.79	2.84	3.43	4.27	-	4.93	-	2.11	4.47
WN Damp, South Wall (18)	-	2.78	3.44	5.48	4.98	6.37	-	2.09	4.47

4.4.3 Through Stockwell transform based method

Processing of the experimental data is carried out according to Section 3.1.4 in terms of time dependent amplification function and average damping ratio assessments. Below, some interesting features of near-real time amplification results are given for Test 6 and Test 9, since in Beyer et al. (2015) those tests are indicated in which the significant damage was accumulated.

Figure 4.13: Post-processing of Test 6 (left) and Test 9 (right) through ST method (*Foun* stands for foundation)

Once we elaborate Figure 4.13, we may observe that at the initiation of each test amplification frequency is more or less in line with white noise elaborations. To be clearer, while for Test 6 it is around 6.7 Hz with respect to 6.4 Hz WN-based measurement carried out before the test and for Test 9 it is around 5 Hz against 5 Hz WN-based measurement done in the pre-test. Moreover, degraded amplification frequency after the strong shaking is in agreement with after test WN-elaboration, too. This value is around 5.4 Hz for Test 6 versus 4.75 Hz WN-based Test 8 elaboration. It should be noted that the effect of Test 7 is also present.

Another interesting observation is in Test 6, Beyer et al. (2015) documented a noteworthy increase in the damage state of the structure in terms of diagonal cracks on the URM walls (Figure 4.14, left). Such response is of brittle nature, and it is observed as the sudden drop of amplification frequency around 14 seconds (Figure 4.14, left). On the other hand, in Test 9, the structure had been evaluated by Beyer et al. (2015) as near-collapse, by noting yielded RC walls and completely failed URM walls (Figure 4.14, right). It had also been commented that RC walls are still far away from failure. As a matter of fact, upon the loss of the URM walls the response observed in Test 9 is ductile and could be observed a gradual decrease of amplification frequency of 5 Hz to around 2 Hz.

Figure 4.14: Damage to URM walls (from Tondelli et al., 2014; <https://zenodo.org/record/11578>)

4.5 Numerical modelling

4.5.1 Simplified numerical model

In this modelling approach, the system is idealized as an equivalent single degree of freedom (SDOF) approach in which the structural response is idealized with hysteretic hardening softening (HHS) model (Borzi et al., 2001). Defined for the response of reinforced concrete members/systems, HHS model is defined by the primary curve associated with unloading and reloading curves. Essentially, for non-degrading systems, the primary curve becomes the backbone curve on which the cyclic load reversals are followed. For the primary curve tri-linear response is defined in which the first line represents the small strain response prior to cracking, the second branch represents the cracked but elastic response, and the last one defines the post-yield response. Unloading and reloading rules consider stiffness degradation under cyclic loading. In other words, the system gets softer as the number of cycles increase and/or the amplitude of inelastic deformation increases. In Figure 4.16 **Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.**, graphical description of the model may be found.

It is important to note that since the building is idealized as SDOF system, corresponding transformations together with associated assumptions, shown below, should be made (Figure 4.15).

Figure 4.15: Conversion of multi degree of freedom system to equivalent degree of freedom system

4.5.1.1 Model setup

Table 4.7 summarizes the parameters assumed in the definition of the simplified model.

Table 4.7: Equivalent SDOF model parameters

Parameter	Definition	Value
W^*	Modal weight	581400 N
F_y^*	SDOF yield strength	390000 N
d_y^*	SDOF yield displacement	0.006 m
F_y^*/F_{cr}^*	Ratio of yield strength to cracking force	3
k_{pl}	Kinematic hardening ratio	0
k_v/k_{cr}	Ratio of cracked stiffness to uncracked stiffness	0.45

Earthquake sequence is applied in the same order of the test without changing any property of the model. In the Figure 4.16, SDOF displacement-normalized base shear response obtained in all tests are shown.

Figure 4.16: Displacement – normalized base shear response for an equivalent SDOF system

4.5.1.2 Model verification with experimental data

Verification of the idealized SDOF model will be made in

Figure 4.17 in terms of (i) 3rd story level acceleration response history during Test 8 (by following the entire sequence of Test 1 to Test 8) and (ii) maximum top displacement of MDOF system in Tests 6, 8, and 9 in which seismic induced deformations are accumulated during the experimental campaign.

Figure 4.17: Verification of equivalent SDOF model. Left: Comparison of acceleration time history response between SDOF model and test data 3rd story. Right: Maximum absolute top displacement predictions of SDOF model (projected to MDOF through multiplication of displacements with G) and test data

It could be observed that reasonable agreement between the acceleration responses is obtained with slight overestimation of displacement demand rate of SDOF system transferred to MDOF domain. Faster inelastic displacement accumulation between Tests 6 and 9 may be due to presence of inconsistencies in the unloading-

reloading response of the SDOF system compared to the model structure. It is noted that the level of overestimation does not change the predicted damage states.

4.5.2 Full numerical model

This section presents the numerical prediction of linear and nonlinear seismic response of a 4-story reinforced concrete / unreinforced masonry building imposed to uniaxial excitation through shaking table tests performed at the EUCENTRE Laboratories (Beyer et al., 2015). The test specimen was subjected to subsequent earthquake motions of increasing intensity. A three-dimensional nonlinear numerical model was implemented and subjected to the input base motions. Appropriate modeling brought in reasonably accurate replication of the observed responses.

4.5.2.1 Calibration

The software platform SeismoStruct 2021 (Seismosoft, 2021) was used to build the numerical model. The test unit's linear and nonlinear dynamic structural behaviour was described with 2-node frame finite element models. A single inelastic force-based frame element represents RC walls and the rectangular beams with effective width. This element is a force-based 3D beam-column element type capable of modelling members of space frames with geometric and material nonlinearities. The sectional stress-strain state of beam-column elements was obtained by integrating the nonlinear uniaxial material response of the individual fibres in which the section has been subdivided, fully accounting for the spread of inelasticity the member length and across the section depth.

An inelastic masonry frame element represents the URM wall. This element is a combination of a 3D, force-based, plastic hinge element type used to model primarily the bending behavior of the masonry member (herein referred to as the 'internal sub-element') and two links at the two edges used to simulate the member's shear behaviour (herein referred to as the 'external links' or 'link sub-elements'). The internal sub-element and the external links are connected in series, ensuring equilibrium in bending moment and shear force. The only 'active' degrees-of-freedom of the link sub-elements are the two translational ones in the shear directions (in-plane and out-of-plane). At the same time, the other four DOFs (axial and three rotational) remain perfectly rigid links. With this configuration, both masonry walls and spandrels may be precisely simulated. The shear DOFs of the link sub-elements feature a hysteretic curve that is based on SeismoStruct's built-in MIMK-pinched nonlinear curve (Modified Ibarra-Medina-Krawinkler deterioration curve with bilinear hysteretic rules and pinching), according to a phenomenological law that describes the shear behaviour of the entire member (Ibarra et al., 2005). Simultaneously, in the internal sub-element, the fiber-section modelling allows for a relatively accurate description of the coupled axial-flexural behaviour. The sectional stress-strain state was obtained by integrating the nonlinear uniaxial material response of the individual fibres. The section has been subdivided, fully accounting for the spread of inelasticity along the member length across the section depth.

The diaphragm effect of the floor slabs was considered by imposing rigid constraints among all the joints belonging to the same slab. The total construction weight, including the additional weight on the slab, was estimated to be around 676 kN without foundation. The added weights were included in the model as lumped masses at the mass centers.

The nonlinear concrete behaviour was represented by a constant-confinement concrete model (Mander et al., 1988; Martínez-Rueda and Elnashai, 1997; Madas, 1993) without considering the tensile strength of concrete; the confinement effect was described by effective confinement stress, which depends on the longitudinal and transverse reinforcement. The reinforcement steel behaviour was characterized by the uniaxial stress-strain relationship proposed by Menegotto and Pinto (1973), coupled with the isotropic hardening rules proposed by Filippou et al. (1983). The force-deformation relationships assumed for concrete and steel were shown in Figure 4.18.

Figure 4.18: Force-deformation relationships used in the analytical models: (a) reinforcement steel, (b) concrete material

The time integration was carried out using the Newmark algorithm with $\gamma = 0.5$ and $\beta = 0.25$ (constant average acceleration method; Chopra, 2012). Inside each time step, convergence was verified; the convergence criterion is based on displacement and rotation: the maximum values (along all the corresponding degrees of freedom) of the ratios between the increments of displacement and rotation and the prescribed tolerances should be less or equal than 1. The displacement tolerance is 10^{-4} m, and the rotation tolerance is 10^{-4} rad. For the sake of avoiding expensive calculations, in each time step, the maximum number of iterations is 300. The damping matrix is proportional to the initial stiffness; the damping ratio was assumed 3.5% for RC members and 7% for masonry walls (based on the calibration of the numerical model). Figure 4.19 displays the numerical model in 3D and elevation view in SeismoStruct 2021 (Seismosoft, 2021). On the top right of Figure 4.19, a perspective view of the experiment was shown (Beyer et al. 2015).

Figure 4.19: 3D and elevation view of the numerical model in the SeismoStruct (2021)

The parameters corresponding to the inelastic masonry frame element were calibrated using the experimental data acquired from the test series on six identical unreinforced masonry walls (Figure 4.20a) by Petry and Beyer (2014; 2019). The experimental campaign comprised six tests on masonry walls that all had the same dimensions. The walls were named PUP1–6 and represented the first story of the shaking table test performed at the EUCENTRE Laboratories (Beyer et al. 2015). The test units were subjected to quasi-static cycles of increasing drift demands (Figure 4.20b); the tests differed concerning the axial load and the moment restraint applied at the top of the walls.

Figure 4.20: Test setup with sign conventions after processing (Petry and Beyer, 2019), b) Loading history

Figure 4.21 displays the force-displacement hysteresis obtained from the conventional measurement devices in the experiment (Petry and Beyer, 2019) and the numerical model (after calibrating procedure) corresponding to the first wall (PUP1) and the second wall (PUP2). The first wall, PUP1, was tested under double-fixed boundary conditions. Hence, the shear span was at approximately $0.5H$. The second wall, PUP2, was tested with a shear span of $0.75H$.

Figure 4.21: Displacement-force hysteresis for numerical model and experiment performed by Petry and Beyer (2019) a) PUP1, b) PUP2

Figure 4.21 confirms that the estimated parameters resulting from the calibration process, for the inelastic masonry frame element can simulate approximately the actual behaviour of the URM walls. More calibrations were conducted based on the structure's overall behaviour to complete the development of the numerical model. Later, utilizing the input excitation of the shaking table test (Beyer et al. 2015), a nonlinear time history (NLTH) analysis was conducted on the numerical model, and the findings were summarized in the subsections below. Before starting the NLTH analysis, the fundamental periods (modal frequencies) were obtained using the classic linear eigenvalue analysis by discretizing the buildings with classical lumped masses models. Table

4.8 and Table 4.9 display the modal frequencies (Hz) corresponding to the numerical model per test for both directions, i.e., north-south and east-west directions (Figure 4.1), respectively.

Table 4.8: Summary of modal frequencies (Hz) corresponding to the full model per test (NS direction)

Test No.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Mode 1	7.12	7.12	7.12	6.56	6.17	5.74	5.65	5.04	4.50
Mode 2	25.39	25.39	25.39	23.40	21.98	20.47	20.15	17.95	16.06
Mode 3	53.91	53.91	53.91	49.71	46.69	43.47	42.79	38.12	34.10
Mode 4	86.23	86.23	86.23	79.50	74.68	69.52	68.45	60.98	54.54

Table 4.9: Summary of modal frequencies (Hz) corresponding to the full model per test (WE direction)

Test No.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Mode 1	3.77	3.77	3.77	3.48	3.27	3.04	2.99	2.67	2.39
Mode 2	8.11*	8.11*	8.11*	7.47*	7.02*	6.54*	6.43*	5.73*	5.13*
Mode 3	12.14	12.14	12.14	11.19	10.51	9.79	9.64	8.58	7.68
Mode 4	21.72	21.72	21.72	20.03	18.81	17.51	17.24	15.36	13.74

*: the second mode in this direction is related to the torsion mode of the building.

Figure 4.22 displays the modal shapes of the building corresponding to the NS direction. Sketches from Figure 4.22 show typical and expected behaviour.

Figure 4.22: Modal shape of the numerical model corresponding to the NS direction.

Figure 4.23 demonstrates the comparison between the fundamental periods obtained from the experiment results (Beyer et al. 2015) and the ones obtained from the numerical model per test for both directions.

Figure 4.23: Comparison between the fundamental periods obtained from different methods using the experiment results and the ones obtained from the numerical model per test for both directions

As can be seen in Figure 4.23, there is a reasonable coherence between the numerical and experimental results in terms of fundamental period. It should be noted that for the west-east direction only the results obtained from the numerical model for the west-east direction were shown in Figure 4.23.

4.5.2.2 Model verification with experimental data

Numerical simulations were conducted using the FEM building model and, sequentially, the complete series of experimental input acceleration. As mentioned before, motions were scaled from 0.05g to 0.9g representing nine sequential tests from minor damage to near collapse states. In addition, the effect of cumulative damage in the numerical model was taken into account by reducing the moments of inertia of RC and URM walls for each test.

Since the main objective of this research is the near real-time seismic damage assessment paradigm with a dependency on damage levels experienced by the building, herein, we established some performance indices for appraising each test. These indices were intended to quantify the analysis results. Three primary magnitudes were selected:

- Drift ratio. The ratio between inter-storey displacement and storey height. This index provides information, for each storey, on the damage of structural members and walls.
- Base shear force. Reports the demanding horizontal force on the foundation.
- Acceleration. This index provides information on the damage to the non-structural components. The acceleration index was correlated to debris fall risk and other similar effects, such as out-of-plane failure of URM walls.

Figure 4.24, Figure 4.25, and Figure 4.26 show two examples regarding the comparison of measured (Test 1 and Test 7) and calculated time-history results in terms of the top displacements (relative to the building base), base shear force, and the absolute accelerations, respectively for the NS loading direction. As mentioned above, relative displacements report structural damage (and to some types of non-structural damage, such as cracking of brittle elements), while the absolute accelerations were directly correlated to non-structural damage.

Figure 4.24: Measured and calculated time-history of the top displacement for NS loading direction a) Test 1, b) Test 7

Figure 4.25: Measured and calculated time-history of the base shear forces for NS loading direction a) Test 1, b) Test 7

Figure 4.26: Measured and calculated time-history of the top floor acceleration for NS loading direction a) Test 1, b) Test 7

Plots from Figure 4.24, Figure 4.25, and Figure 4.26 show that the analytical results of the specimen match the experimental results, reasonably. Convincing results can also be seen in Figure 4.27, which shows the acceleration envelopes for the eight runs. This figure shows the comparison between positive and negative acceleration envelopes derived from the numerical simulation and the experiment per test for NS loading direction.

Figure 4.27: Comparison between positive and negative envelopes derived from numerical simulation and experiment per test for NS loading direction

The plots of Figure 4.27 depicted that for the low to medium reference intensity level (i.e., Test1-Test4), the acceleration profiles corresponding to the experiment results and the numerical ones have almost similar shapes for positive and negative direction (NS loading direction). For larger intensity levels (i.e., Test 5-Test 8), the acceleration profile obtained from numerical simulation is relatively similar for the negative direction. However, for the positive direction, the numerical results provide almost underestimated values. This consequence might be related to either input modelling parameters, coupling effects, strain rate effects in dynamic testing, analysis program capabilities, or a combination of these factors. However, it is not possible to isolate the source with the available data.

4.5.2.3 Interstory drift comparison

The distribution of damage over the building's height may also be seen in the structure's drift profiles. Figure 4.28 shows the drift profiles for the eight runs corresponding to the numerical results. These drift profiles are envelopes of the positive and negative drift demands, which were in the following referred to as maximum and minimum peak drifts. Negative drifts were associated with a displacement in the negative direction (towards north) and positive drifts with a positive direction (towards south).

Figure 4.28: Peak inter-storey drift envelopes

The plots in Figure 4.28 show that for $PGA \leq 0.4g$ (i.e., Test1-Test5 and Test 7), the drift profiles are approximately symmetric. This symmetrical behaviour depicts the structure's elastic behaviour, which is in line with the findings of Beyer et al. (2015). For $PGA > 0.4g$ (i.e., Test 6 and Test 8), the drift profiles in the positive and negative direction differ. For loading in the positive direction, the behaviour was controlled by the RC walls. As a result, the drift profiles are similar to cantilever wall drift profiles under lateral loading, with the biggest drifts towards the top of the wall. For loading in the negative direction, the URM walls control the behaviour.

Finally, in Beyer et al. (2015) the relationship between maximum roof drift and maximum interstorey drift relation is studied.

4.6 Comparison of period of vibrations and damage states along longitudinal direction

Bilinearly approximated pushover curves presented in Beyer et al. (2015) express an average yield drift of 0.125% and a complete failure drift of 0.90% defining the nonlinear character of the structure. Those values will be used with Lagomarsino and Giovinazzi (2006) framework.

$$DG = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } \Delta/H < 0.09\% \\ 1 & \text{if } 0.09\% \leq \Delta/H < 0.20\% \\ 2 & \text{if } 0.20\% \leq \Delta/H < 0.52\% \\ 3 & \text{if } 0.52\% \leq \Delta/H < 0.9\% \\ \geq 4 & \text{if } 0.9\% \leq \Delta/H \end{cases} \quad (4.1a)$$

Where Δ and H corresponds to average drift and building height. Residual average drift is linked to the maximum drift through the equations.

Beyer et al. (2015) studied the correlation between maximum roof drift to maximum inter-storey drift. Overall, Equation (4.1a) may be restated as in Equation (4.1b).

$$DG = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } \Delta s/h < 0.09\% \\ 1 & \text{if } 0.09\% \leq \Delta s/h < 0.30\% \\ 2 & \text{if } 0.30\% \leq \Delta s/h < 0.8\% \\ 3 & \text{if } 0.8\% \leq \Delta s/h < 1.4\% \\ \geq 4 & \text{if } 1.4\% \leq \Delta s/h \end{cases} \quad (4.1b)$$

Where Δs and h corresponds to interstorey drift and story height. Residual average drift is linked to the maximum drift through the equations.

Limit states for residual roof drifts could be written as:

$$\Delta_r = 0 \text{ if } \Delta \leq \Delta_y ; 0.3(\Delta - \Delta_y) \text{ if } \Delta_y < \Delta < 4\Delta_y ; (\Delta - 3\Delta_y) \text{ if } 4\Delta_y \leq \Delta \quad (4.2a)$$

$$DG = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } \Delta_r/H = 0.0\% \\ 1 & \text{if } 0.0\% < \Delta_r/H < 0.02\% \\ 2 & \text{if } 0.02\% < \Delta_r/H < 0.13\% \\ 3 & \text{if } 0.13\% < \Delta_r/H < 0.51\% \\ \geq 4 & \text{if } 0.51\% \leq \Delta_r/H \end{cases} \quad (4.2b)$$

In Table 4.10, results of each method are presented in terms of inverted vibration periods, drift predictions (when applicable), and damage grade predictions based on EMS98 scale according to the approaches defined in Section 3.2.

Table 4.10: Calculated and measured (measured values are taken from Beyer et al., 2015) vibration periods, calculated damping ratios, calculated and observed damage states (observed states are taken from Beyer et al., 2015).

Method & Damage Estimation Approach	Test	Calc. T(s)	Test T(s)	DR (%)	T/T ₀	Approach 1		Approach 2			Approach 3	Obs. Dam.
						DG P1%	DG P2%	$\delta\Delta_{max}$ (%)	$\delta\Delta_r$ (%)	DG	DG	
FDD & Damage Estimation Approaches 1 and 3	WN 1	0.13	0.13	-	1.00	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	WN 2	0.13	0.13	-	1.00	D0 97%	-	-	-	-	≤D1	≤D1
	WN 3	0.13	0.13	-	1.00	D0 97%	-	-	-	-	≤D1	≤D1
	WN 4	0.15	0.15	-	1.15	D1 77%	D2 17%	-	-	-	≤D1	≤D1
	WN 5	0.19	0.16	-	1.46	D2 78%	D3 13%	-	-	-	D2	D2
	WN 6	0.16	0.17	-	1.23*	D1 57%	D2 37%	-	-	-	D2	D2
	WN 8	0.21	0.19	-	1.62	D2 67%	D3 24%	-	-	-	D2	D2
	WN 9	0.20	0.21	-	1.53	D2 75%	D3 18%	-	-	-	D2	D3
	EFDD & Damage Estimation Approaches 1 and 3	WN 1	0.13	0.13	0.005	1.00	-	-	-	-	-	-
WN 2		0.13	0.13	0.005	1.00	D0 97%	-	-	-	-	≤D1	≤D1
WN 3		0.13	0.13	0.005	1.00	D0 97%	-	-	-	-	≤D1	≤D1
WN 4		0.15	0.15	0.005	1.15	D1 77%	D2 17%	-	-	-	≤D1	≤D1
WN 5		0.18	0.16	0.055	1.39	D2 74%	D1 12%	-	-	-	D2	D2
WN 6		0.16	0.17	0.005	1.23*	D1 57%	D2 37%	-	-	-	D2	D2
WN 8		0.21	0.19	0.090	1.62	D2 67%	D3 24%	-	-	-	D2	D2
WN 9		0.20	0.21	0.050	1.53	D2 75%	D3 18%	-	-	-	D2	D3
Wavelet WN & Damage Estimation Approaches 1 and 3		WN 1	0.12	0.13	0.018	1.00	-	-	-	-	-	-
	WN 2	0.13	0.13	0.028	1.08	D1 47%	D0 45%	-	-	-	≤D1	≤D1
	WN 3	0.13	0.13	0.034	1.08	D1 47%	D0 45%	-	-	-	≤D1	≤D1
	WN 4	0.15	0.15	0.043	1.25	D1 50%	D2 43%	-	-	-	D2	≤D1
	WN 5	0.17	0.16	0.050	1.42	D2 77%	D3 11%	-	-	-	D2	D2
	WN 6	0.16	0.17	0.049	1.33	D2 65%	D1 25%	-	-	-	D2	D2
	WN 8	0.19	0.19	0.021	1.58	D2 71%	D3 21%	-	-	-	D2	D2
	WN 9	0.20	0.21	0.045	1.67	D2 62%	D3 27%	-	-	-	D2	D3
	Wavelet Tail & Damage Estimation Approaches 1 and 3	GM 1	0.14	0.13	0.009	1.00	-	-	-	-	-	-
GM 2		0.15	0.14	-	1.06	D0 65%	D1 30%	-	-	-	≤D1	≤D1
GM 3		0.15	0.15	0.029	1.07	D0 55%	D0 38%	-	-	-	≤D1	≤D1
GM 4		0.15	0.15	0.027	1.07	D0 55%	D0 38%	-	-	-	≤D1	D2
GM 5		0.14	0.14	0.056	1.00	D0 97%	-	-	-	-	≤D1	D2
GM 6		0.27	0.23	0.038	1.92	D3 44%	D2 34%	-	-	-	D2	D2
GM 7		0.22	0.22	0.035	1.57*	D2 72%	D3 20%	-	-	-	D2	D2
GM 8		0.32	0.26	0.041	2.29	D4 47%	D3 46%	-	-	-	D3	D3
GM 9		0.39	0.29	0.052	2.79	D4 81%	D3 19%	-	-	-	≥D4	≥D4
Stockwell Amp. & Damage Estimation Approaches 1 and 3	GM 1	0.14	0.13	0.040	1.00	-	-	-	-	-	-	≤D1
	GM 2	0.15	0.14	0.040	1.07	D0 55%	D1 38%	-	-	-	≤D1	≤D1
	GM 3	0.15	0.15	0.050	1.07	D0 55%	D1 38%	-	-	-	≤D1	≤D1
	GM 4	0.16	0.15	0.050	1.14	D1 77%	D2 14%	-	-	-	≤D1	D2
	GM 5	0.17	0.14	0.080	1.21	D1 63%	D2 32%	-	-	-	≤D1	D2
	GM 6	0.18	0.23	0.055	1.29	D2 55%	D1 37%	-	-	-	D2	D2
	GM 7	0.18	0.22	0.090	1.29*	D2 55%	D1 37%	-	-	-	D2	D2
	GM 8	0.20	0.26	0.075	1.42	D2 77%	D3 8%	-	-	-	D2	D3
	GM 9	0.48	0.29	0.155	3.42	D4 98%	-	-	-	-	≥D4	≥D4
Numerical SDOF + Stockwell & Damage Est. App. 1 & 2 & 3	GM 1	0.13	0.13	-	1.00	-	-	0.01	0.00	-	-	≤D1
	GM 2	0.14	0.14	-	1.08	D1 47%	D0 45%	0.02	0.00	D0	≤D1	≤D1
	GM 3	0.15	0.15	-	1.15	D1 77%	D2 17%	0.04	0.00	D0	≤D1	≤D1
	GM 4	0.14	0.15	-	1.08	D1 47%	D0 45%	0.06	0.00	D0	≤D1	D2
	GM 5	0.15	0.14	-	1.15	D1 77%	D2 17%	0.09	0.00	D1	≤D1	D2
	GM 6	0.19	0.23	-	1.46	D2 78%	D3 13%	0.20	0.01	D2	D2	D2
	GM 7	0.21	0.22	-	1.62	D2 67%	D3 24%	0.18	0.01	D2	D2	D2
	GM 8	0.23	0.26	-	1.77	D2 51%	D3 35%	0.42	0.08	D2	D2	D3
	GM 9	0.43	0.29	-	3.30	D4 97%	-	1.10	0.01	≥D4	D3	≥D4
Full Numerical & Damage Est. Approach 2	GM 1	0.14	0.13	-	-	-	-	0.01	0.00	D0	-	≤D1
	GM 2	0.14	0.14	-	-	-	-	0.03	0.00	D0	-	≤D1
	GM 3	0.14	0.15	-	-	-	-	0.05	0.00	D0	-	≤D1
	GM 4	0.15	-	-	-	-	-	0.09	0.00	D1	-	D2
	GM 5	0.14	-	-	-	-	-	0.15	0.00	D1	-	D2
	GM 6	0.23	-	-	-	-	-	0.30	0.00	D2	-	D2
	GM 7	0.22*	-	-	-	-	-	0.16	0.01	D2	-	D2
	GM 8	0.26	-	-	-	-	-	0.46	0.02	D2	-	D3
	GM 9	0.29	-	-	-	-	-	NC	NC	NC	-	≥D4

NOTES: Approach 1 is empirical, Approach 2 is numerical, Approach 3 is analytical. In the case of full numerical model, interstorey drifts are used over the average roof drift. NC stands for "not get a convergence for this test". *: In a sequential analysis, any damage grade cannot be smaller than previous. Colour code is consistent with Figure 3.2 and Figure 3.3

Following comments could be made in terms of fundamental vibration periods and damping ratios obtained through different approaches:

- Noise-based frequency domain interpretations (FDD and EFDD) of pre-test vibration periods provide good comparisons with the experimental data present in the relevant publication,
- There is a good agreement between CWT based interpretations of vibration periods using the tail of the test when it is compared with the experimental data and the other signal approaches both in terms of white noise and strong motion treatment,
- Stockwell-transform based approach provides reliable evolution of vibration periods with increasing intensities,
- Damping ratios obtained through EFDD are strongly dependent on the number of Fourier terms adopted. From the point of view of stability, a simple dynamic amplification-based approach is giving more consistent results. Wavelet-based interpretations of damping using the tail of the test or the white noise are not consistent and currently cannot be used for an automatic identification of damage. On the other hand, wavelet-based interpretations combined with RD technique seems promising, although further investigations are necessary before deciding if this can be used for damage identification. It is noted that a significant scatter in estimation of damping ratio is observed even when the RD procedure is used. This could be due to the fact that in damping estimation, the evaluation of RD signature for such a non-stationary and short duration record does not represent the free decay response of the structure. At this stage, Authors discourage the use of damping ratio as a damage assessment proxy due to unconsolidated findings.

Following comments could be made in terms of the damage estimations:

- Use of FDD and EFDD seem encouraging when it comes to the near real-time damage estimation. Yet, it should be noted that to utilize those methods with their maximum applicability, a good quality noise information is needed,
- Wavelet based interpretation of damage is producing reliable results in near real-time,
- Stockwell transform based time-dependent amplification ends up with damage evolution over time, estimating the end damage states in a reliable manner with small overestimation of intermediate damage states. Moreover, it may predict if the damage evolution is ductile (spread over time) or brittle (sudden). It works well in near real-time. In order to utilize the method with maximum performance, low-noise acceleration time histories should be present both at roof and foundation levels,
- Comparison between estimated damage using the complete numerical model (Full model) and the observed damage through the experiment shows a good agreement and confirms the reliability of the calibrated model. In case of detailed knowledge, model updating scheme is an excellent tool,
- In case of limited knowledge available, simplified modelling may be a good alternative to obtain reasonable comparable damage estimates in significantly smaller amount of time with respect to full modelling. Moreover, analytical approach would also provide a good feedback mechanism,
- In case of basic knowledge, empirical approach provides probability of damage in a consistent manner, however, dispersion should always be noted (i.e., the most probable and second most probable damage states should be taken into consideration).

5 REAL-LIFE APPLICATIONS

Within the framework of the TURNkey project, Bucharest was chosen as a testbed (i.e., TB1), considering the peculiarities and the hazard posed by the Vrancea seismic area. 15 TURNkey multi sensor units (15 accelerometric sensors RS4D and 5 GNSS sensors) were deployed in 5 building types representing 3 different generations of earthquake resistant design codes, in order to assess the structural response and to understand how the seismic design evolved over a period of 80 years and how vulnerable are different structural typologies.

As described in the following section, a database of recordings has been built by collecting signals recorded during recent earthquakes at TB1 (Bucharest). The first set of data consists of a collection of real signals recorded on a mid-height reinforced concrete structure by broadband sensors. The second set consists of signals recorded on different types of structures (masonry and reinforced concrete buildings) monitored with RS4D sensors (belonging to the TURNkey unit). The processing for both the datasets has been then carried out by adopting the approaches tested in Section 4 to provide a real case study real-life applications of the algorithms adopted in the methodological framework set-up in Task 4.3. It is noted that the damage estimation is not possible due to weak nature of the recorded motions. Due to this reason, only dynamic identification results will be provided.

5.1 Background information

Bucharest, the capital city of Romania, is a city exposed to a high level of seismic hazard, controlled mainly by the Vrancea intermediate-depth seismic source. The most recent destructive earthquake that affected Bucharest occurred on March 4th, 1977. More than 30 mid to high-rise buildings have collapsed totally or partially, producing more than 1400 casualties in the capital city alone.

5.1.1 Specification and instalment of the sensors

Despite the restrictions imposed due to the COVID-19 pandemic, all the fifteen RS4D sensors were installed in June-July 2020. The four GNSS receivers and antennas were deployed in November 2020, while the fifth one was installed in March 2021. All stations were configured to forward data to the TURNkey platform server hosted at Gempa (GMP). In addition, the CAPS data compression module was implemented in the units and the data stream will be rerouted to the Gempa CAPS system.

A sixth building was added afterwards as a case-study for the project, due to its long-term instrumentation with professional accelerometers and the building owner is one of the stakeholders interested in the TURNkey platform.

5.1.1.1 Broadband sensors

The Institute of Atomic Physics building (IFA or TURN) is located in Magurele, close to Bucharest. The building was completed in 1974, it was partially damaged by the 1977 earthquake, and it was retrofitted afterwards. The monitoring system consists of three accelerometers installed at the basement, 6th floor and 10th floor. The three TSA-100S tri-axial accelerometers and a 24-bit Digitizer (iDAS) were installed in December 2013 and all the data are transmitted in real-time to the INFP's Data Center, for archiving and post-processing.

Figure 5.1: TSA-100S tri-axial accelerometer and iDAS Digitizer as installed on the TURN building

For this building, the free-field reference seismic station is considered BUC1, located 340 meters away from the structure.

5.1.1.2 RS4D sensors

The RS4D is a well-rounded, strong motion seismograph. With multiple sensors, more data options, and a wider range it has a multitude of applications, including those that require an accelerometer.

The RS4D has three orthogonally positioned microelectromechanical systems (MEMS) accelerometers built into the board and a professional-grade vertical seismometer called a geophone.

Figure 5.2: Raspberry Shake 4D sensor (three-component MEMS accelerometer and one vertical geophone) and the installation setup for Bucharest, with power supply, protection and GPRS router

Figure 5.3: The manufacturer self-noise of the RS4D-V6 sensors, left – velocity channel and right – acceleration channels (Raspberry Shake RS4D Technical Specifications Sheet). Information on the instrumented buildings

Even though the geophone is incredible sensitive due to its low value of self-noise (Figure 5.3, left), for strong motion the geophone velocity sensor can be “saturated” or exceeding the instrument’s measurement limit. The integrated MEMS accelerometer should remain in scale for strong motion, with the cost of a high level of self-noise, as presented in Figure 5.3, right. The two types of sensors are complementary and proved to work well together.

5.1.2 Information on the instrumented buildings

The evolution of the design regulations in Romania was directly related to the major seismic events that occurred in the past, with their effects and also to the advancement of construction industry and computation capabilities. From this perspective, given the large number of old buildings exposed to high levels of seismic hazard in Bucharest, the main idea was to instrument and gather data about the most representative typologies, depending on the materials and construction period.

5.1.2.1 Layout of all buildings on GIS map

Table 5.1 presents the buildings instrumented by INFP, in TB1 (Bucharest) within the TURNkey project, using 15 RS4D sensors and five GNSS receivers and antennas. The Raspberry Shake code is also presented, together with the position of the sensors and a map showing the spatial distribution is presented in Figure 5.4.

Table 5.1: Instrumented buildings by INFP in Bucharest in the framework of TURNkey project

Address	Nr. of sensors	Accelerometer position	Raspberry shake code
a) Titan (TIT)	3	ground floor	AM.R7CA2
		5 th fl.	AM.R7270
		10 th fl. (roof)	AM.RAB6A
b) Vasile Lascar Str. (LAS)	4	3 rd basement	AM.R7A63
		ground floor	AM.R8BAF
		5 th fl.	AM.R2768
c) Brasov Str. (DRT)	3	11 th fl.	AM.R26B4
		ground floor	AM.R13FF
		5 th fl.	AM.R36C6
d) Locotenent Aurel Botea Str (BAL)	2	9 th fl.	AM.R59F6
		basement	AM.RD1CA
		attic	AM.R2EA6
e) Pescarusului Str. (DRT)	3	basement	AM.RB536
		5 th fl.	AM.R4601
		8 th fl.	AM.SDB1E

Figure 5.4: Map of the TURNkey RS4D locations, free-field and building stations of the Romanian Seismic Network

5.1.2.2 Building typologies under consideration and relevant information

Five buildings were selected to be instrumented in the framework of the TURNkey project, in Bucharest, as follows:

- A pre-code (before 1963) low-rise (basement (B), ground floor (GF) and attic) masonry building (BAL). This building was constructed even before 1940, has masonry structure with wooden floors and the data collected from this building will help us to understand the general dynamic behaviour of the low-rise old buildings from Bucharest Area subjected to intermediate-depth Vrancea earthquakes.

Figure 5.5: Google Earth view and picture of the BAL building

- A pre-code (before 1963) high-rise (>8 stories) RC building - (DRT) reinforced concrete frames and panels of reinforced concrete

Figure 5.6: Google Earth view and picture of the DRT building

- A low code (1963 – 1977) high-rise (>8 stories) RC building - (TIT) reinforced concrete panels with reinforced concrete shear walls

Figure 5.7: Google Earth view and picture of the TIT building

- A moderate code (1978 – 1992) high-rise (B + GF + 8 stories) RC building (DRG). The building was erected in 1982 and it is a residential building. During that period, a lot of these types of buildings were constructed in Bucharest to accommodate all the population that moved to the capital city.

Figure 5.8: Google Earth view and picture of the DRG building

- A high-code (>1992) high-rise (3B + GF + 11 stories) RC frame building (LAS). This is a new office building, completed in 2008 and designed according to the new design code that was aligned with the Eurocode 8 Part I seismic design code (EN 1998-1, 2004).

Figure 5.9: Google Earth view and picture of the LAS building

- The sixth building was briefly described in Section 5.1.1.1

Figure 5.10: Google Earth view and picture of the TURN building

5.1.2.3 Sensor locations and directions with respect to the structural orientation

In Table 5.2, there are schematic representations of the sensor orientations toward the main axes of the buildings, with respect to the geographical North or East directions. A more comprehensive description of the Romanian Seismic Network, with a focus on Bucharest area, both for free-field and instrumented structures, including software and hardware components was presented in the TURNkey Deliverable D2.3 Report on seismic ground motion and urban infrastructure monitoring systems across TBs.

Table 5.2: Sensor orientations and directions with respect to the structural orientation and the geographical North

5.1.3 Seismotectonic nature of Bucharest, site conditions at monitored locations, and EQ info

Romania is an active seismic country and Bucharest is one of the most earthquake-endangered capitals in Europe. One-to-six strong magnitude earthquakes occurred in Romania every century, the most recent ones being 1940 and 1977 that affected the city. Bucharest is located in the central part of Plain Vlasia, which is part of the Romanian Plain, and is approximately 165km from Vrancea epicentral zone. Thick unconsolidated sedimentary layers in the area of Bucharest amplify the seismic shear-waves, which may cause severe destruction. In the city, Dambovitza valley looks like a long corridor approximately 22 km long. Its width varies

from 650 m opposite the Botanical Garden, to about 4 km at the eastern end of the village Catelu (before being regularized in the last century). There are lakes in the city, for example at the Park Carol and Youth Park, on the right bank of Dambovița, and Lake Cismigiu on the left bank. The lake “Lacul Morii” (the Lake of the Mill) is an unusual feature, formed by the dam on river Dambovita in the Ciurel zone, in the 20th century. A list of the most recent earthquakes, starting with the multi-sensor deployment campaign within TURNkey, is presented in Table 5.3.

Table 5.3: Earthquakes that occurred in Romania after the deployment of the instruments (June 2020), with $M_L > 3.8$

EQNO	DATE	TIME	DEPTH	M_L	M_W
1	02-Jun-2020	11:12:58	101.3	4.5	4.1
2	21-Jun-2020	03:47:27	119.4	4	3.8
3	25-Jun-2020	17:30:16	12.4	4.5	3.4
4	15-Aug-2020	02:28:54	125.1	3.9	3.7
5	28-Aug-2020	21:21:45	15.8	3.7	3
6	10-Oct-2020	06:29:47	65.8	4	3.8
7	22-Oct-2020	20:21:44	122.1	4	3.8
8	29-Oct-2020	22:39:37	9.1	4.2	3.3
9	03-Nov-2020	09:14:41	117.7	3.9	3.7
10	27-Nov-2020	12:30:16	124.9	3.8	3.6
11	23-Dec-2020	14:27:17	126.2	3.8	3.6
12	05-Jan-2021	23:50:34	9.6	4	3.2
13	14-Feb-2021	17:24:52	126.2	3.8	3.6
14	24-Feb-2021	02:35:09	133.9	4	3.8
15	27-Feb-2021	21:13:11	124.8	4.2	3.9
16	07-Mar-2021	09:52:28	144.5	4.1	3.8
17	07-Mar-2021	22:34:28	144.9	3.9	3.7
18	23-Mar-2021	06:26:54	121.3	3.8	3.6
19	09-Apr-2021	18:36:47	79	4.6	4.2
20	18-Apr-2021	10:03:16	134.7	3.8	3.6
21	25-May-2021	21:30:37	131.2	4.7	4.3

The largest earthquakes that were recorded by the TURNkey network in Bucharest (April 9th, 2021, and May 25th, 2021) are detailed in the next sections.

5.1.3.1 Event 1

The April 9th earthquake had occurred in the Vrancea intermediate-depth seismic zone, at 21:36:47 (local time) and at a depth of 79 km. The earthquake was located 156 km North of Bucharest and its maximum epicentral intensity was III MMI. The earthquake was felt on the Romanian territory and the maximum recorded acceleration by the Romanian National Seismic Network was 4.4 cm / s².

The TURNkey network configuration and a first visual data quality check are presented in Figure 5.12, for both velocity and acceleration channels. For the velocity channels, it seems that all the sensors located upside-down were not able to properly record the seismic signal (Bad quality data), whereas for the acceleration channels the high value of the instrument self-noise has masked, according to a preliminary visual check, for most of the sensors, the seismic signal (Bad S / N ratio).

Figure 5.11: ShakeMap for the April 9th, 2021, earthquake, in terms of intensity (left) and peak ground acceleration (right)

April 9th Earthquake ($M_L = 4.6$) velocity

April 9th Earthquake ($M_L = 4.6$) acceleration

Figure 5.12: RS4D recording setup and their data availability and quality check for the April 9th, 2021, earthquake for the velocity and acceleration channels

5.1.3.2 Event 2

The May 25th earthquake had occurred in the Vrancea intermediate-depth seismic zone, at 00:30:37 (May 26th local time) and at a depth of 131 km. The earthquake was located 126 km North of Bucharest and its maximum epicentral intensity was IV MMI. The earthquake was felt on the Romanian territory and the maximum recorded acceleration by the Romanian National Seismic Network was 6.6 cm / s².

Figure 5.13: ShakeMap for the May 25th, 2021, earthquake, in terms of intensity (left) and peak ground acceleration (right)

The TURNkey network configuration and a first visual data quality check are presented in Figure 5.14, for both velocity and acceleration channels. For the velocity channels, as in the previous case, all the sensors located upside-down were not able to properly record the seismic signal (Bad quality data), whereas for the acceleration channels most of the sensors have recorded a useful signal, given that the magnitude and the acceleration values were larger for the May 25th earthquake.

Figure 5.14: RS4D recording setup and their data availability and quality check for the May 25th, 2021, earthquake for the velocity and acceleration channels

5.2 Sample data acquired and corresponding detailed analysis for 2 selected buildings

In this section, sample noise (Section 5.2.1) and signal level information is provided for the building with high precision sensors (TURN) and one representative building with low-cost RS4D sensors. The dataset consisted in acceleration and velocity data for the two events. Five-minute-long recordings, centered on the earthquake signals, were selected from the continuous data-flow, at a rate of 100 sps, and analyzed.

5.2.1 Noise level investigation

Figure 5.15: Pre-earthquake seismic noise recordings by using professional sensors, in blue (left) for the April 9th earthquake and RS4D acceleration channels on the East-West direction, in red and the professional sensors, in blue (right) for the May 25th earthquake

A comparison of the ambient noise level for the professional sensors (TURN) and RS4D acceleration channels (TIT building) is presented in Figure 5.15, for the basement, intermediate floor, and top floor. The maximum value of the seismic noise for the TSA-100S sensors is, for the basement, 0.01 cm/s^2 and it is increasing with elevation up to 0.04 cm/s^2 . For the RS4D sensors (red), the level of the self-noise is around 1 cm/s^2 , an amplitude that will make it impossible to record the low-amplitude or ambient vibrations.

This type of result is typical when one compares low-cost versus high-cost instruments since there is a trade-off between their costs and precisions. While being significantly more noisier, with the self and installation costs of 1 broadband high precision sensor setup (i.e., Kinematics ETNA2 Strong Motion Accelerograph), about 4 (four) RS4D setups could be installed which allows obtaining a better distribution of seismic impact during the aftermath of an earthquake, assuming three to four sensors installed on each structure.

5.2.2 Time-history of accelerations (and velocities) for all available floors

Figure 5.16: Acceleration time-histories for the April 9th earthquake, by using TSA-100S seismic sensors

Figure 5.17: DRG building RS4D acceleration channels recordings (red) and TURN building sensors (blue) at the basement, intermediate floor and top, on E-W direction, for the April 9th earthquake

Figure 5.18: The LAS building recordings of the velocity vertical channels, for the April 9th earthquake

Figure 5.19: TIT building RS4D acceleration channels recordings (red) and TURN building sensors (blue) at the basement, intermediate floor and top, on E-W direction, for the May 25th earthquake

Figure 5.20: The DRG building recordings of the velocity vertical channels, for the May 25th earthquake

5.2.3 Graphical elaboration of the signal level data through SHM methods

In this section, sample evaluation is shown for two buildings: TURN (with TSA-100S sensors) and DRG (with RS4D sensors). Summary of the results is provided in Table 5.4 and Table 5.5.

5.2.3.1 Through FDD

With a compromise in the assumption that the input motion is white noise, FDD is performed to view the singular values of multi-channel data from the RS4D device arrays as well as the high-fidelity system instrumented at the TURN building. The singular values from TURN building confirm the high signal-to-noise ratio of the high-fidelity instrumentation, whereas it can be observed that spectral features from RS4D are under stronger influence from the signal noise. As a result, the spectral features pointed out from RS4D is less significant, in other words, the spectral peaks are relatively cumbersome to observe. The Figure 5.21 presents the spectral features (first singular values) from the RS4D-instrumented buildings and TURN building as a reference obtained under two earthquakes took place on April 9th and May 25th.

Looking at the exemplary cases, e.g., DRG and IFA (TURN building), one can note that even if not under ambient vibration, RS4D's still have the potential to provide useful data to identify dynamic characteristics of the observed building. However, the feasibility depends on the level of vibration and low-amplitude events may not generate sufficient vibration to support identification processes. Other than these, the technique is naturally subject to criticism when used under non-white noise, therefore, it is deemed more appropriate to use a technique which incorporates input motion as well as outputs (for example, stochastic subspace identification). However, these techniques need additional process when subject to high noise, and they can be computationally expensive, necessitating the use of computationally efficient single-output techniques as pursued in this report.

One can note that singular value spectrums alone may be insufficient features to determine modal characteristics but can be supported with the mode shapes obtained from the eigenvectors of the singular value

decomposition procedure. In presence of mode shapes, one can confirm whether a particular frequency has a mode shape in line with the expected ones (e.g., triangular increment in the first mode shape). In this way, non-structural candidates can be further eliminated, or modal peaks can be confirmed with reasonable mode shapes.

Figure 5.21: Singular values from FDD under two consecutive earthquakes.

5.2.3.2 Through EFDD

Identification of natural vibration frequency of TURN building is successful by using the environmental noise data. On the other hand, for the majority of the cases, EFDD algorithm fails to identify the singular values in

environmental noise recorded by RS4D sensors. This is due to the fact that those instruments possess significant levels of digital noise as shown in Figure 5.3. As a workaround solution, we attempted to use the tail of the acceleration data using which as the input for EFDD algorithm. This solution worked; however, we do not encourage the use of output only method beyond its ambient/white noise domain. In this respect, the results obtained through tail interpretation should only be used to compare the vibration frequencies obtained with other methods: Wavelet Transform and Stockwell Transformation amplification. In Figure 5.22 below, we are providing an example plot to compare normalized singular values calculated through ambient noise and motion-tail inputs for both TURN and DRG buildings.

Figure 5.22: Normalized singular values obtained in EFDD algorithm shown for a representative building with RS4D sensors (DRG) and for the building with high precision sensors (TURN). Input data is either Ambient Noise (AN) or Ground motion tail that does not include input seismic frequencies.

5.2.3.3 Through Continuous Wavelet Transform based method

For the Bucharest buildings, for computing the period with wavelet analysis, we used only the sensor located on the top floor of each building. We use wavelet analysis approach to estimate the period from the two earthquakes recorded for the buildings instrumented with two types of sensors: Broadband, high quality sensors and RS4D sensors. All the frequencies (Table 5.4 and Table 5.5) are consistent with regard to the results of the EFDD and ST methods, the only significant difference is for the first direction of the building DRT. For DRT building we have tried different parameters of the wavelet in order to separate the frequencies around the 2.8 Hz. We think that for the DRT building, the frequencies in the two principal directions are very close and it is difficult to separate them. Using wavelet analysis, we cannot estimate the period from the tail (the last 10 seconds of the earthquake) for the buildings instrumented with RS4D Sensors (Figure 5.24), but this is possible for the building instrumented with Broadband, high quality (Figure 5.23).

Earthquake: Filter_up_RO.TURN3.HNx.dat (Acc. 1)

Tail (10sec): Filter_up_10sec_RO.TURN3.HNx.dat

Figure 5.23: TURN building response for one direction using Wavelet approach during 9 April 2021 Earthquake (top –earthquake and down –tail of 10 seconds); signal recorded with Broadband, high quality sensors.

Earthquake: Filter_up_AM.RAB6A.ENx.dat (Acc. 1)

Tail (10sec): Filter_up_10sec_AM.RAB6A.ENx

Figure 5.24: TIT building response for one direction using Wavelet approach during 9 April 2021 Earthquake (top –earthquake and down –tail of 10 seconds); signal recorded with RS4D Sensors.

5.2.3.4 Through Stockwell Transform Approach

In this section, Stockwell transform based identification of fundamental vibration frequency is provided for the buildings monitored through high precision sensors and RS4D sensors. It must be noted that for high precision sensors, algorithm works as expected, however for RS4D counterpart real-time amplification is highly dependent on the level of noise of both top and bottom receivers. As a consequence of having a high level of noise in both locations, spurious amplifications are also computed alongside the correct ones. In Figure 5.25 to Figure 5.27, we are presenting the results for TURN, DRG, and TIT buildings which may be considered as excellent, acceptable, and poor dynamic identifications, in the respective order. Complete set of identified frequencies for all buildings are given in Table 5.4 and Table 5.5.

Figure 5.25: Analysis of TURN building response using Stockwell Transform approach during 9 April 2021 Earthquake. Left: Horizontal-X direction, right: horizontal-y direction. Example for good dynamic identification.

Figure 5.26: Analysis of DRG building response using Stockwell Transform approach during 25 May 2021 Earthquake. Left: Horizontal-X direction, right: horizontal-y direction. Example for acceptable dynamic identification.

Figure 5.27: Analysis of TIT building response using Stockwell Transform approach during 9 April 2021 Earthquake. Left: Horizontal-X direction, right: horizontal-y direction. Example for poor dynamic identification.

5.2.4 Comparisons of the fundamental vibration periods of all buildings

We are providing the results of dynamic identifications obtained through the methods under consideration.

Table 5.4: Summary of f_0 (Hz) information during 9 April 2021 Earthquake. Note that in some cases, x and y natural frequencies are close to each other, they are identified as identical.

Method	Direction	Buildings					
		TURN	DRG	TIT	LAS	DRT	BAL
EFDD with ambient noise	f0x (Hz)	1.6	-	-	-	-	-
	f0y (Hz)	1.6	-	-	-	-	-
EFDD with tail or whole motion	f0x (Hz)	1.6	2.3	2.1	1.4	-	-
	f0y (Hz)	1.6	-	2.1	-	1.95	-
Stockwell-amplification	f0x (Hz)	1.6	2.3	2.0	1.5	2.5	-
	f0y (Hz)	1.6	3.5	2.5	1.3	2.1	-
FDD with whole motion	f0x (Hz)	1.59	2.32	1.98	1.34	2.69	5.03
	f0y (Hz)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Wavelet full	f0x (Hz)	1.52	2.21	1.86	1.36	2.77	4.92
	f0y (Hz)	1.55	3	2.38	1.2	1.94	5.56
Wavelet with tail	f0x (Hz)	1.54	-	-	-	-	-
	f0y (Hz)	1.56	-	-	-	-	-

Table 5.5: Summary of f_0 (Hz) information during 25 May 2021 Earthquake

Method	Direction	Buildings					
		TURN	DRG	TIT	LAS	DRT	BAL
EFDD with ambient noise	f_{0x} (Hz)	1.6	-	-	-	-	-
	f_{0y} (Hz)	1.6	-	-	-	-	-
EFDD with tail or whole motion	f_{0x} (Hz)	1.6	2.1	2.1	1.2	-	-
	f_{0y} (Hz)	1.6	2.7	2.1	-	2.5	-
Stockwell-amplification	f_{0x} (Hz)	1.6	2.3	-	1.3	2.5	9.1
	f_{0y} (Hz)	1.6	3.4	-	1.3	2.1	6.4
FDD with whole motion	f_{0x} (Hz)	1.59	2.32	1.98	1.34	2.69	5.03
	f_{0y} (Hz)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Wavelet full	f_{0x} (Hz)	1.56	2.17	1.96	1.33	2.77	5
	f_{0y} (Hz)	1.53	3.48	2.36	1.23	1.85	6.25
Wavelet with tail	f_{0x} (Hz)	1.54	-	-	-	-	-
	f_{0y} (Hz)	1.52	-	-	-	-	-

In Table 5.4 and Table 5.5, apart from BAL, vibration periods estimated through earthquake motion-based approaches agree sufficiently with each other. Moreover, period of vibration values inverted by these methods are verified by FDD and EFDD approaches, as well. Better inversion of vibration period for BAL is expected during a stronger event.

5.2.5 Estimated earthquake moment magnitude to create better signal over noise ratios

As it is discussed up to now, the weak nature of the recorded motions and high self-noise levels of the RS4D sensors are posing some limitations in the signal processing phase. While the solution of the latter is related to the processing algorithms that can be tested and validated on laboratory data, the former may be overcome with a dataset recorded for a stronger event which generates motions with higher signal to noise ratios, suitable for the application of the proposed methodology in real-life case-studies from Bucharest. If one considers the scenario of the 1977 Vrancea earthquake (7.4 M_w), one of the most destructive earthquakes that hit Romania, some conclusions can be drawn based on the ground motion model (GMM) of Vacareanu et al. (2015).

The epicentre of the earthquake was located at about 160 km NE of Bucharest. By setting the epicentre in the same place as the 1977 earthquake and assuming two scenarios in terms of earthquake's depth: 90 km and 150 km, one should notice that for a 5.0 M_w event the expected ground motion, according to the Vacareanu et al. (2015) GMM, will be 6.2 cm / s^2 for the first case and 4.4 cm / s^2 for the second case. In other words, considering the self-noise limit of the RS4D sensors being 1 cm / s^2 , a 5.0 M_w seismic event at a depth of 90 km will generate, for the instrumented buildings in Bucharest, a maximum S/N of about 6 and for a depth of 150 km, the expected S/N will be about 4, in terms of PGA. These values should satisfy the signal processing criteria in order to extract the fundamental periods of the structures. However, according to the fragility functions for the most conservative of the instrumented structures (LAS), detailed in Deliverable 4.2 (Pavel et al., 2018), none of these acceleration values, most probably, will not lead to the occurrence or exceedance of the slight damage in structures (as the probability of exceedance is very low for a PGA value of 0.5 % g), so the structures will be identified in undamaged conditions. One of the overall ambitions of the TURNkey platform is to provide an efficient procedure for rapid prediction of losses immediately following an earthquake. The added value of the RS4D sensors data will be of critical importance in TB-1 (Bucharest), for strongest earthquakes that generate a ground motion capable to induce a certain level of damage (at least slight) in structures and to modify their dynamic parameters accordingly.

6 CONCLUSIVE REMARKS

In this report, two noise based (FDD and EFDD) and two ground motion based (Wavelet Transform and Stockwell Transformation) approaches are used as structural health monitoring methods to identify the initial and damaged natural fundamental vibration frequency of the structural systems under consideration. Then damage prediction is made based on the frequency ratio considering the reduced and initial values. Damage assessment is carried out according to EMS98 damage grades and three different approaches for damage assessment are proposed: (i) empirical approach based on the dataset present in Goulet et al. (2015), (ii) numerical approach based on simplified SDOF (ii.a) and complete modelling schemes (ii.b), and (iii) analytical approach based on the concept of secant stiffness. To select the method to be utilized, following guidelines may be used based on the level of knowledge available:

- Basic knowledge level: Basic (empirical) approach (compatible with LoDA 1 and 2 of TURNkey Deliverable D4.1)
- Intermediate knowledge level: Basic, simplified numerical, and analytical approaches (Compatible with at least LoDA 3 of Deliverable D4.1)
- Detailed knowledge level: All approaches including the detailed numerical modelling, as well (much higher than LoDA 3 of Deliverable D4.1).

It is worth mentioning that the set-up tools are able to work in the framework of rapid response to earthquakes (RRE). The basic approach can work in a few minutes, thus in near real-time the outcomes of the approaches can be displayed in the platform. For the Intermediate level, a reasonable estimate of time required to carry out the analysis is in the order of minutes. The required time for detailed knowledge level, is difficult to be *a-priori* estimated, since it depends on the characteristics of the structure under consideration (such as the size, configuration, etc.) as well as the available data for charactering the material properties and the computational platform adopted for carrying out the analysis.

The main aim of this Deliverable is the development/testing of the algorithms/tools for damage detection. For the near-real time damage detection, there are at least two other issues related to the instrumentation and to the IT system that should be managed: (i) the acquisition of the signal in real/near-real time related to the instrumentation tasks (i.e., WP2) and (ii) integration of the algorithms developed here in a IT systems related to the WP6.

The report contains two principal Sections: Section 4 and Section 5. In the former, SHM approaches are validated against comprehensive dataset of sequential dynamic tests carried out on EUCENTRE Shake table by considering a model 4 story reinforced concrete unreinforced wall masonry structure through the use of detailed data present in Beyer et al. (2015). Following the benchmarking of SHM methods, damage estimation methods are tested and validated against experimental observations.

In Section 4, we noted that frequency reduction could be efficiently linked to estimated damage, while damping ratio assessment does not seem to give consistent results. Furthermore, in case the level of information allows, the assistance of numerical modelling may help significantly to the precision of the expected damage results. Such numerical modelling may be carried out in a simplified manner (through iterative initial setup of parameters) or in detailed manner (through model updating procedure). In this section, all structural health monitoring approaches and damage prediction methods are verified with experimental data.

It could be concluded from Section 5 that the identification of the natural vibration frequencies of the monitored buildings are completed. It is important to note that the level of noise present in RS4D sensors prevents the use of output only FDD and EFDD approaches during dynamic identification under ambient vibration. Although the effects of this noise reduce when a building is subjected to earthquakes, violating the output-only condition may necessitate alternative techniques (e.g., short-time multi-input multi-output approaches, time-frequency techniques). Due to this limitation, these noise-based techniques should be utilized for only TURN building on which high precision sensors are installed. High level of noise present in RS4D sensors affected also Wavelet Transform based and Stockwell Transformation approaches. Yet, since they

operate in the ground motion domain, stronger earthquakes creating more intense motion would result in better functionality due to increased signal-to-noise ratios. Once the damaging earthquake occurs, damage proxies will be calculated based on the approaches presented in Section 4. In this respect, considering the Approach 2, there is an ongoing work of the creation of an idealized SDOF model for the monitored structures. At the current moment, development of a complete numerical model is not compatible with the level of knowledge available. It should be also noted that after a damaging event, residual drifts may be tracked with GNSS sensors, to compare the numerical models under consideration. From the performance limits perspective, the framework of Lagomarsino and Giovinazzi (2006) seems promising with adoption of structure specific yield and ultimate average drifts.

Once the EMS98 damage grades of the instrumented buildings are estimated, for each building class typology under consideration, we recommend using the conceptualization made in Deliverable D4.1 concerning the shift of mean damage function of Giovinazzi (2005) with the feedback of sensor-based damage data by using the taxonomy classification made in Deliverable D4.2.

To sum up, with this report we are suggesting the use of Wavelet-energy based and Stockwell transformation based strong ground motion-based approaches for the evaluation of the vibration periods as primary SHM methods. Yet, it has been also showed that, although the domain of input motion appears to be outside of those approaches, FDD and EFDD based output-only approaches are still helpful to verify the values of vibration periods obtained with other two approaches. During the processing with FDD and EFDD, care must be paid to be sure that mode shapes are reasonable and inverted periods of vibrations are repeatable. In case of future availability of detailed knowledge level, advanced numerical modelling will be carried out case by case basis by the Partners as it is not compatible with automatization.

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APPENDIX 1: TIME-FREQUENCY DOMAIN ANALYSES

In this Appendix, the results of post-processing figures of Section 4 and Section 5 are provided for Wavelet and Stockwell transformation approaches.

Figures considering EUCENTRE Shake Table Benchmark Tests considering Stockwell Transformation

Figures considering Bucharest considering Wavelet Transformation

1. 9 April 2021, Eq

1.1 TURN, Broadband, high quality sensors

Earthquake: Filter_up_RO.TURN3.HNx.dat (Acc. 1)

Tail

(10sec): Filter_up_10sec_RO.TURN3.HNx.dat

Earthquake: Filter_middle_RO.TURN3.HNx.dat (Acc. 2)

Tail (10sec): Filter_middle_10sec_RO.TURN3.HNx.dat

1.2 TIT, RS4D Sensors

Earthquake: Filter_up_AM.RAB6A.ENx.dat (Acc. 1)

Tail (10sec): Filter_up_10sec_AM.RAB6A.ENx

Earthquake: Filter_middle_AM.RAB6A.ENx.dat (Acc. 2)

Tail (10sec): Filter_middle_10sec_AM.RAB6A.ENx

Earthquake: Filter_down_AM.RAB6A.ENx.dat

1.3 LAS, RS4D Sensors

Earthquake: Filter_up_AM.R26B4.ENx (Acc. 1)

Tail (10sec): Filter_up_10sec_AM.R26B4.ENx

Earthquake: Filter_middle_AM.R26B4.ENx

Tail (10sec): Filter_middle_10sec_AM.R26B4.ENx

Earthquake: Filter_down_AM.R26B4.ENx

1.4 DRT, RS4D Sensors

Earthquake: Filter_up_AM.R59F6.ENx

Earthquake: Filter_middle_AM.R59F6.ENx

1.5. DRG, RS4D Sensors

Filter_up_AM.SDB1E.ENx

Filter_middle_AM.SDB1E.ENx

1.6. BAL, RS4D Sensors

Filter_up_AM.R2EA6.ENx

Filter_middle_AM.R2EA6.ENx

2. 25 May 2021, Eq

2.1 TURN, Broadband, high quality sensors

Earthquake: Filter_up_RO.TURN3.2021.145.HNx (Acc. 1)

Tail (10sec): Filter_up_10sec_RO.TURN3.2021.145.HNx

Earthquake: Filter_middle_RO.TURN3.2021.145.HNx (Acc. 2)

Tail (10sec): Filter_middle_10sec_RO.TURN3.2021.145.HNx

2.2 TIT, RS4D Sensors

Earthquake: Filter_up_AM.RAB6A.2021.145.ENx (Acc. 1 -f0x)

Tail (10sec): Filter_up_10sec_AM.RAB6A.2021.145.ENx

Earthquake: Filter_middle_AM.RAB6A.2021.145.ENx

Tail (10sec): Filter_middle_10sec_AM.RAB6A.2021.145.ENx

2.3 LAS, RS4D Sensors

Filter_up_AM.R26B4.2021.145.ENx

Filter_middle_AM.R26B4.2021.145.ENx

1.4 DRT, RS4D Sensors

Filter_up_AM.R59F6.2021.145.ENx

Filter_middle_AM.R59F6.2021.145.ENx

1.5 DRG, RS4D Sensors

Filter_up_AM.SDB1E.2021.145.ENx

Filter_middle_AM.SDB1E.2021.145.ENx

1.6 BAL, RS4D Sensors

Filter_up_AM.R2EA6.2021.145.ENx

Filter_middle_AM.R2EA6.2021.145.ENx

Figures considering Bucharest considering Stockwell transformation (RS4D sensors only)

